

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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IMPROVING EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT THROUGHPUT:
INITIATION OF A NEW STANDARD PROTOCOL,
A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Overcrowding in the emergency department (ED) happens when the number of patients exceed the capability of the ED to safely and efficiently provide quality care within a reasonable time frame (Canadian Association Canadian Association of Emergency Physicians [CACAEP], 2018). In 2016, California's EDs handled 14.6 million visits, an increase of 44% within a 10-year period, causing patient dissatisfaction, long wait times, poor patient outcomes, and higher morbidity and mortality rates (Chow, Niedzwiecki, & Hsia, 2017; O'Connor, Gatién, Weir, & Calder, 2014; Stauber, 2013). Using a standardized protocol (SP) can help reduce ED overcrowding (Bakhsh, 2015; Hwang, Payton, Weeks, & Plourde, 2016; Lindley-Jones & Finlayson, 2000; Stauber, 2013). This DNP quality improvement project utilized a pre- and post-intervention design for creating a new SP to alleviate ED overcrowding and improve throughput and ED metrics. For this project, an electronic self-learning module (ELM) was developed to teach ED triage nurses how to implement this new, evidenced-based standard protocol (SP) that equips them to approach a patient's symptomatology and chief complaints in an organized, systematic problem-solving approach. The new SP initiates diagnostic testing and implements therapeutic management regimens during triage prior to the ED physician's initial assessments. Upon implementation, the anticipated outcome is that the new SP will help (a) reinforce effective triaging, (b) expedite patient flow, (c) improve

patient safety, and (d) improve throughput. The new SP can be implemented in any ED. Together, both the ELM and the new SP should help improve any hospital's ED metrics.

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BACKGROUND

In 2016, California emergency departments (ED) served 14.6 million patient visits, an increase of 44% within 10 years (California Health Care Almanac [CHCA], 2018). The American College of Emergency Physicians [ACEP] (2016) reported that ED overcrowding has been a major problem and has many negative effects that interrupt patient treatments and outcomes. It has been a major cause of patient dissatisfaction, medication errors, long wait times, delayed treatments, poor patient outcomes, and higher morbidity and mortality rates (ACEP, 2016; Bakhsh, 2015; Chow et al., 2017; Salway, Valenzuela, Shoenberger, Mallon, & Vicellio, 2017).

Overcrowding in the ED occurs when the number of patients exceeds the capability of the ED to safely and efficiently provide quality care within a reasonable time frame (Canadian Association of Emergency Physicians [CAEP], 2018; Stauber, 2013). A study in Australia found that there was a 30% increase in patient mortality due to overcrowding (Sprivulis, Da Silva, Jacobs, Frazer, & Jelinek, 2006). Research also has suggested that there were additional factors that can contribute to ED overcrowding, such as a high volume of patients, non-urgent visits, inappropriate use of the ED, and staffing shortages (Salway et al., 2017; Vezyridis & Timmons, 2014; Weiss, 2014).

A standardized protocol can help mitigate these factors that contribute to ED overcrowding. A standardized protocol (SP) is an evidenced-based set of medical orders developed as a guideline for specific patient conditions or complaints (Hwang et al., 2016; Retezar, Bessman, Ding, Zeger, & McCarthy, 2010). In response to the problem of ED overcrowding, many hospitals have been utilizing a standardized protocol for triage that is initiated by designated triage nurses. The purpose of this project's proposed SP is

to initiate diagnostic testing and implement simple therapeutic management regimens during triage prior to the ED physician's initial assessments. This may help improve the efficiency of ED throughput by having diagnostic test results completed to help expedite physician decision-making, thus reducing wait times (Hwang et al., 2016; Lindley-Jones & Finlayson, 2000). The initiation of a SP has the potential to increase patient flow, improve patient safety, and decrease length of stay (LOS) (Bakhsh, 2015).

Problem Statement

ED overcrowding has been a problem at a small acute care intercommunity hospital in Orange County. The hospital's ED metrics times of (a) door-to-decision times (DTD), (b) door-to-admit times (DTA), and (c) door-to-discharge times (DTDC) are longer and (d) left without being seen (LWBS) rates have been higher than the national average (Appendix A). A significant factor causing overcrowding in emergency rooms and its negative effects on quality of care, has been the lack of an effective standardized protocol for the triage process. Therefore, this project proposes a new triage model to help improve ED flow and throughput.

Significance of the Problem

In the project hospital, 26,000 patients on average were seen in the ED per year. The ED has 11 beds with an average census of 1,700 patients a month (ED Director, personal communication, May 3, 2018). In looking at the project hospital's current data compared to the national data, the project hospital's ED metrics (Figure 1) times for door-to-decision was 33 minutes longer, while door-to-admit time was 49 minutes longer, and door-to-discharge times were 42 minutes longer (ProPublica, 2018). The project hospital's data showed that the ED had a higher LWBS rate (Figure 2), which

currently has been at 6%, compared to the national average of 2% (ED Director, personal communication, May 3, 2018; ProPublica, 2018).

Figure 1. Project hospital ED metrics: Door-to-decision, door-to-admission, door-to-discharge compared to national average

Figure 2. Project hospital ED metrics, 2018 Left without being seen.

A linear relationship was noted when the worst metrics were associated with higher census days, or when the ED was crowded (Figure 3). With long wait times and a high LWBS percentage in this small ED, it had become imperative that changes to front-end ED throughput should occur. One of the ways to improve metrics is to initiate and evaluate a new triage process.

Figure 3. Project hospital ED metrics, 2018: Patient census.

Purpose Statement

The aim of this doctoral quality improvement (QI) project is to improve ED throughput by implementing and evaluating a new standardized protocol (SP) for treatment and diagnostics for triage. Once this QI project has commenced, the throughput process will be addressed by improving outcome measures of ED metrics for: DTD, DTA, DTDC and LWBS rates. This DNP project addressed the implementation of a new SP to improve ED throughput and help alleviate ED overcrowding. An electronic self-learning module (ELM) was developed and designed by the project investigator to train the triage nurses on the new SP. Once implemented, the ED nurses will have to take this

mandatory self-learning module before they can be eligible to perform the role of a triage nurse. The initiation of the new SP for triage is expected to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the existing triage process.

Supporting Framework

The plan-do-study-act cycle, originally conceptualized by Dr. Walter Shewart in 1939 and modified by Dr. Edward Deming in 1950, is a systematic process for integrated learning and improvement model. It consists of four cycles: (a) plan, (b) do, (c) study, and (d) act (PDSA) (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2018; Moen & Norman, 2010; The W. Edwards Deming Institute, 2019). The Deming Institute has stated the framework allows for (a) changes to be made on a small scale, (b) evaluations to be made before moving forward with further changes, and (c) repetition of the PDSA cycle until the goal is met. It allows the leadership team to evaluate the progress of the change, offering feedback and encouragements to the staff as part of the change process (Spence & Cappleman, 2011; The Deming Institute, 2019).

Using the PDSA framework, Sheaff, Sherriff and Hennessy (2018) conducted a study on developing and strengthening dementia patients' residential environment. This was done by training the caregivers using the PDSA cycle to test interventions by coordinating activities that increased their dementia awareness as well as their awareness on how they managed patient care. Key players were identified, and meetings were held to implement multiple new activities through small-scaled initial testing. These new activities produced positive results of high "well-being scores" from the different dementia learning communities that were being measured.

Goulding et al. (2015) used the PDSA model to try to improve hand-over report from the intensive care unit nurses to the general floor nurses. Implementation of an electronic “iMobile” report included a verbal and written critical care discharge summary. The researchers conducted three cycles of PDSA. The first cycle consisted of (a) planning, (b) identifying the gaps, (c) producing process mapping, and then (d) auditing the discharge summaries. The second PDSA cycle (a) tackled problems addressed from the audits, (b) created a literature review, and (c) examined the feasibility of an electronic discharge summary. The third PDSA cycle was intended to look at the data regarding the discharge summaries provided by the nurses. It was found to be lacking pertinent information. The plan was to provide educational sessions to assist the nurses in writing and delivering appropriate discharge summaries. The PDSA model helped the researchers apply the steps and evaluations needed when implementing a change in process in increments of small scales and repeated cycles.

This proposed project endeavor is to implement change to the current triage process in order to improve ED throughput. A well-conducted investigation with steps of implementation and evaluation would be beneficial in the execution of this proposal. Therefore, the PDSA framework served as the guide for this QI project. Figure 4 has provided the breakdown of the individual sections of PDSA.

Plan

According to Moen and Norman (2010), the model starts with knowing the plan or what is needed to be changed or improved. The framework also details the measurable outcomes, identifies the stakeholders and provides the timeframe for the implementation.

PDSA Model courtesy of The W. Edwards Deming Institute®

Figure 4. Plan-do-study-act theoretical framework.

Do

The second step is *do*, where the intervention or the change occurs (Moen & Norman, 2010). The Deming Institute (2018) suggested starting the project on a small scale to identify any problems or obstacles before moving forward. Implementation, documenting observations and data collection begins in the “do” phase.

Study

Study and analyzing the data and findings, is the third step (Moen & Norman, 2010). According to The Deming Institute (2018), this is where all data collected will be evaluated to determine if the process helped. A comparison of results to what was predicted and a summary of what was learned is disclosed. The investigator also looks closely for any unintended consequences (Moen & Norman, 2010).

Act

The last cycle is to *act* on the results by determining if the change will be adopted, modified, or abandoned (The Deming Institute, 2018). Will the cycle test be repeated? Are the results positive or negative? At this point, the project is either (a) adopted (results are positive and the intervention is kept), (b) abandoned (results are negative; change the approach and repeat the cycle again to see other results), or (c) adapted (results are negative; modify the process and repeat the cycle) (The Deming Institute, 2018; Moen & Norman, 2010; Sheaff, et al., 2018).

The use of the PDSA framework assisted and guided this project investigator to develop and prepare to implement this proposal in a thorough and systematic manner. With any change, it is always important to assess whether the change is working or not; therefore, the need for constant evaluation and modification has been the emphasis of this theory (The Deming Institute, 2018; Moen & Norman, 2010; Sheaff, et al., 2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Methods

A review of literature was conducted to gather the latest research applicable to this quality improvement project. A table of evidence for this project is listed in Appendix B. The database was accessed through the California State University Fullerton (CSUF) Pollak library website. Multiple databases were utilized to search for publications relevant to the subject of emergency department (ED) throughput. Databases used were: CINAHL Plus, PubMed, EBSCO, Science Direct, Google Scholar, Google search engine, and CSUF's *OneSearch*, which is a data-accessing tool that searches four California State University database systems (Marcel, 2017).

A literature search was performed to find studies or papers on ED standards and metrics. An in-depth search for ED throughput studies were done using the websites: American College of Emergency Physicians (ACEP), Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS), Center for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], Emergency Nurses Association [ENA], ER Wait Watcher [ERWW], National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS), and Office of Statewide Health Planning and Development [OSHPD]. Table 1 has listed the databases with the different topics searched, key words used, and outcomes of results retrieved.

Inclusions to the search parameters were peer-reviewed articles, English only articles, and articles published within the last 15 years. The references of retrieved articles were also examined for further relevant research. The overall topics for the review of literature were: (a) emergency department overcrowding, (b) emergency department throughput interventions, (c) emergency department triage, (d) standard

protocols, (e) triage protocols, (f) nursing protocols, (g) emergency department saturation, and (h) emergency department metrics. Key search terms included:

Table 1

Cumulative Results from OneSearch and PubMed Database Searches

Topic	Search Terms	Articles Retrieved	
		OneSearch	PubMed
Emergency Department	flow	43,665	2343
	throughput	3,982	309
Throughput: Overcrowding	overcrowding	2,716	366
	throughput AND overcrowding	308	22
Metrics	metrics	658	705
	wait times	826	854
	throughput AND left without being seen	794	4242
Standard Protocol	Standard protocol AND triage	18,669	156
	Standard protocol AND triage AND overcrowding	921	25
Standardized Procedures	Standardized Procedures AND emergency room AND triage	3,841	156
	standardized procedure AND emergency department, AND medication errors	12,539	46
	standard protocols AND triage AND interventions	5,361	301
Electronic Online Learning	Electronic Online Learning AND triage	2,209	2
	Online Class AND triage	5,017	1
	Online Class AND triage AND learning	2,085	0
Continuing Education Provider	Continuing Education Provider AND Nursing	27,709	957
	Continuing Education Provider AND Nursing AND Triage	1,377	0

overcrowding, standardized protocols, standardized procedures, triage order set, ED metrics, diagnostic tests in triage, and triage protocol.

For the educational contents used in creating the ELM, literature search was performed to find information for online education, electronic online learning, triage class, creation of a PowerPoint presentation, Bloom's taxonomy, as well as becoming a continuing education provider with the Board of Registered Nurses (BRN).

Emergency Department Overcrowding

In 2016, there were 14.6 million ED visits in California (CHCA, 2018). For California, this was an increase in patients seen in 2014 (13.3 million) and 2015 (14.2 million) (Office of Statewide Health Planning and Development [OSHPD], 2016). This influx of patients caused ED overcrowding. The ACEP (2016) reported that greater than 90% of EDs regularly had overcrowded conditions. Overcrowding can lead to multiple negative consequences such as long wait times, increases in length of stay (LOS), increases in ambulance diversions, increases in patient boarding (defined as admitted patients staying in the ED due to a lack of available hospital beds), and increases in medication errors (ACEP, 2016; Bakhsh, 2015; Chow, et al., 2017; Cooper, Datner, & Pines, 2008; Salway et al., 2017; Vezyridis & Timmons, 2014; Weiss, 2014). A retrospective study done by Chow et al. (2017) concluded that the trend of ED overcrowding suggested that there was an inadequate supply of ED beds that cannot keep the pace with the growing demands of acutely sick patients who seek emergency services; therefore, improvements must be made to meet this need.

Research has shown that overcrowding has caused "sepsis bundles being affected...delay (or failure) to administer antibiotics in community acquired pneumonia, poor analgesia management in patients with severe pain, increased medical errors, and increased mortality" (ACEP, 2016, p. 4). Fee, Weber, Maak, and Bacchetti (2007) found

that ED overcrowding negatively affected the time antibiotics were administered for patients with community-acquired pneumonia (PNA). The study also noted that if the ED was at full capacity of 30 patients, only 55.8% of the patients received their antibiotics within the four-hour time frame; if the ED had 40 patients, there would be only 46.4% of PNA patients that would receive their antibiotics within the suggested four hours.

Salway et al. (2017) found 76% of acutely ill patients reported a decrease in patient satisfaction when they were not seen in a timely manner. Salway et al. (2017) and Vezyridis and Timmons (2014) both found that increased wait times caused more patients to leave the ED without being seen by the ED physician. These patients also ended up returning to the ED later and were more severely ill.

Research also has shown that ED overcrowding has been associated with increases in the morbidity and mortality rate (10.7%), compared to times when the ED is not crowded (8.4%) (Bakhsh, 2015; Houston, Sanchez, Fischer, Volz, Wolfe, 2015); Salway et al., 2017; Vezyridis & Timmons, 2014). A study conducted by Pines and Hollander (2009) showed during times of ED overcrowding, patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) had a 3% higher mortality rate related to cardiac death and cardiac complications such as heart failure, arrhythmias, strokes, and hypotension compared to non-crowded EDs.

Emergency departments have much to improve when monitoring triaged patients in the waiting room as they wait to be examined by ED providers (Bakhsh, 2015; Salway et al., 2017; Stauber, 2013). Crowding has resulted in an inability to triage in a timely manner due to the large number of patients waiting to seek medical services (Bakhsh,

2015). Patients in the waiting room or hallway have been insufficiently monitored, a safety issue that has caused poor patient outcomes (ACEP, 2016; Bakhsh, 2015). The Centers for Disease Control (CDC) reported that over 10% of patients triaged by a nurse and categorized as critical waited for more than an hour to be seen by a provider (Bakhsh, 2015; CDC, 2016). Another crucial factor that has contributed to poor outcomes are errors in accurately triaging patients (Betz, Stempien, Trivedi, & Bryce, 2017; Houston, Sanchez, Fischer, Volz, Wolfe, 2015; O'Connor, et al., 2014). A study conducted by Wolf, Delao, Perhats, Moon and Zavotsky (2017) found that distress with environmental conditions, such as overcrowding, triage nurses can become overwhelmed, leading to inaccurate triaging.

Standardized Protocol

Although the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS, 2016) currently has not mandated any protocol or orders for patients with specific problems, institutions have had policies in place for SP that apply to advance triage practices (ACEP, 2016; Domagala & Vets, 2015). Following implementation of a strict set of guidelines, diagnostic interventions, as well as any additional simple therapeutic interventions, can be ordered by the trained triage nurse (ACEP, 2016; Ebrahimi, Mirhaghi et al., 2016; Stauber, 2013). The goal of the SP is to initiate patient treatments and diagnostic testing before the patient is seen by the physician, especially when the ED is crowded (Domagala et al., 2015; Retezar et al., 2010; Robinson, 2013). Multiple studies have shown that having a SP can be cost-effective as well as enhance patient comfort and reduce patient LOS and treatment times (ACEP, 2016; Begaz, Elashoff, Grogan, Talan,

& Taira, 2016; Buttigieg, Dey & Cassar, 2016; Chan, Killeen, Kelly, & Guss, 2005; Domagala et al., 2015; Ebrahimi et al., 2016; O'Connor et al., 2014; Retezar et al., 2010).

Douma, Drake, O'Dochartaigh, and Smith (2016) evaluated nurse-initiated protocols in multiple busy and overcrowded EDs and found the use of SP improved the timeliness of care for specific patient complaints. They found that the SP improved (a) time to diagnostic testing, (b) time to medication administration, and (c) decreased overall LOS. The study found that the patients who had nurses who did not use a SP waited to receive medications an average of five times longer than patients whose nurses had utilized a SP. For example, administration of acetaminophen for fever and pain was decreased by 186 minutes when the SP was utilized. The study also evaluated chest pain patients and showed that a SP decreased troponin result time by 79 minutes. Hip fracture patients went to x-ray in 42 minutes versus 299 minutes, which correlated with a decrease of LOS by 224 minutes. Vaginal bleeds during pregnancy decreased LOS by 232 minutes with the initiation of a pregnancy protocol consisting of a serum hemoglobin level, Rh typing, and *B*-human chorionic gonadotropin testing. Abdominal pain had a 181 minutes difference in LOS with the use of SP (which was not specified in the article).

The research literature also found that the benefits of having a SP resulted in faster patient flow, shorter wait times, and expert triaging in the ED (Begaz et al., 2016; Buttigieg et al., 2016; Chan et al., 2005; Ebrahimi et al., 2016; O'Connor et al., 2014; Retezar, et al., 2010; Robinson, 2013; Stauber, 2013). Chan et al. (2005) conducted a study with the initiation of a new protocol labeled rapid entry and accelerated care at triage (REACT). The results for six months after REACT implementation demonstrated improvement in all ED metrics: DTD decreased 31 minutes, DTDC reduced by 35

minutes, DTA reduced by 11 minutes, total wait times also were shown to be reduced by 35 minutes and LWBS rates significantly decreased by 42% ($p < .001$). Retezar et al. (2010) implemented a study to assess if initiating SP in triage decreased treatment time. The research showed that it did decrease the treatment time by 16 % and decreased LOS times by 12%.

Begaz et al., (2016) performed a prospective randomized controlled trial to examine the effects of initiating diagnostic tests in the waiting room, specifically on the total LOS in the ED and the LWBS rates. Patients who received diagnostic testing while in the waiting room had a significant shorter mean time (245 minutes) in the ED once they got to their ED room, than those who received no interventions (277 minutes). They also had a shorter overall LOS by 44 minutes. The LWBS rate was also less in those patients who received diagnostic tests (78 of 848 patients) compared to the group that did not receive any diagnostic testing (103 of 811 patients). Therefore, the researchers concluded that initiating diagnostic testing in the waiting room decreased the time spent in ED bed, decreased total LOS, and decreased LWBS rates. Initiating diagnostic testing improved ED throughput.

Evidenced-Based Standard Protocol Interventions

A patient's chief complaint can be quickly assessed given the appropriate guidelines and resources. Standardized protocols consist of systematic order sets and guidelines for medication administration and diagnostic testing. Such interventions on a SP can be initiated by the triage nurse.

Many life-saving diagnostic tests such as the 12-Lead Electrocardiogram (EKG) are among the SP interventions. According to American Heart Association Practice

guidelines for the management of patients with acute myocardial infarction, recommendations for any patient presenting to the ED with the complaint of chest pain (CP) or angina pain should receive an EKG within 10 minutes upon arrival to the ED (American Heart Association [AHA], 1999). Zègre-Hemsey, Sommargren, and Drew (2011) found that only 41% of patients with an ischemic event had an EKG done within 10 minutes. Zègre-Hemsey et al. (2011) claimed that the reason for the delay could be due to ED overcrowding and not having a set protocol in place. This then reinforces the importance of having a SP in triage, especially a cardiac SP.

Standard protocols also have provided patients with earlier initiation of medical treatments (Cabilan & Boyde, 2017; Cooper, Datner, & Pines, 2008; Hanna, Rohatgi, Shekhani, Dave & Johnson, 2016; Sayah, Rogers, Devarajan, Kingsley-Rocker, & Lobon, 2014). Utilization of the SP to get a chest x-ray (CXR) prior to the provider's examination allowed pneumonia (PNA) patients to receive antibiotics in a timely manner (Cooper et al., 2008; Fee et al., 2007). Cooper et al. study results showed the time to antibiotics for admitted patients with PNA decreased from 4.2 hours to 3.4 hours ($p=.01$). It also showed an increase of patients who received antibiotics within the first four hours increased from 51% to 68% ($p=.05$). A study by Cabilan and Boyde (2017) showed ED patients received analgesics for moderate to severe pain by a mean of 30 minutes faster, had better patient satisfaction, and had 58% more pain relief.

Asthma protocols used in triage have shown to be beneficial for patients having an acute asthma attack (Qazi, Saleh, Tamim, & Serrano, 2010). A pre-post comparison study with 254 patients conducted by Qazi et al. found that a nurse-initiated nebulization treatment decreased door-to-first nebulization time by a mean of 31 minutes. Also

improved were subsequent nebulizer treatment (reduced by 22 minutes) along with door-to-steroid administrations time (reduced by 28 minutes) and nurse re-evaluation (reduced by 16 minutes).

The review of literature also found that for small hospitals with limited resources, the initiation of a SP can be a start to decreasing wait times and improve standards of care (ACEP, 2016; Cabilan & Boyde, 2017; Douma et al., 2016; Qazi et al., 2010). Lindley-Jones and Finlayson (2000) found that pre-treatment x-rays done in triage (a) decreased patient wait time (36% reduction in waiting time; 95% CI 30.2 to 44.2, $p=0.002$). (b) increased patient satisfaction, and (c) provided a sense of teamwork among staff. Another study reported the initiation of radiography using the Ottawa Ankle Rule (OAR), a clinical decision tool for ankle radiography in a tertiary center ED, led to a statistically significant 20-minute decrease in the median LOS (Lee, Filiatrault, Abu-Laban, Rashidi, Yau, & Liu, 2016).

Studies in literature have shown that the use of an ED triage SP was a promising intervention for timely, high-quality patient care and was beneficial in improving all ED metrics. With many of the diagnostic tests completed and medical management initiated, the patient process was expedited. Once the patient was seen by the physician, all diagnostic results were available so that medical decisions can be formulated in a timely manner, leading to improved ED throughput.

Electronic Self-Learning Module

Online learning has been part of a new, evolving pedagogy. In 2013, a survey revealed that 7.1 million university students have taken an online course (Parrish, 2016). Electronic self-learning modules (ELM) have a variety of instructional frameworks which

target audiences based on class content and student population learning styles (Parrish, 2016). In developing an ELM, the teaching method selected is based upon effectiveness, cost efficiency, and the targeted audience. There have been several studies conducted that have evaluated the delivery method of information provided in ELMs. Delivery methods have ranged from textbook narratives to voice-over PowerPoints. A randomized control trial conducted by Franklin, Gubrud-Howe, Sideras and Lee (2015) found that pre-licensed nursing students preparing for their simulation tests rated voice-over PowerPoints as more effective in improving their self-efficacy than reading assignments alone.

Another study conducted by Khasawneh, Simonsen, Snowden, Higgins and Beck (2016) compared medical students who received three different forms of teaching modalities: (a) a text-book form narration, (b) PowerPoint, and (c) voice-over PowerPoint. The study results showed there was no significant difference in improving medical knowledge on the topic of pediatric congenital infections when using the three modalities. The study did show that there was a significant improvement in the students' confidence levels after the use of the two PowerPoint modalities. The students were more satisfied with the two PowerPoint modalities than the textbook narrative. The textbook narrative was not perceived to be helpful by the students.

Rankin, Then, and Atack (2013) conducted an experimental study in which two group of nurses were compared using an online training format to determine triage accuracy. The online training taught the nurses how to use the Canadian Triage Acuity Scale (CTAS). Both the control group and the experimental group received the online tutorial and completed the Online Learner Support Instrument Questionnaires (OLSI).

However, the experimental group also participated in online discussions and conducted a work project (an in-service or a poster-presentation, or a pamphlet) targeting peers. The researchers performed a retrospective chart audit. An expert triage nurse then compared the triage accuracy scores from the two groups with the auditor's triage scores. The researchers found that there were no statistically significant differences between the two group scores ($p=.33$) on the OLSI. Some of the nurses ($n=20$) indicated that the online training did not provide enough time to learn the CTAS while at work. There were 60% ($n=44$) of the nurses who did like taking the training session during work hours. Overall, 78% of the nurses ($n=97$) felt their knowledge of triage had improved. A total of 367 charts were audited by the triage expert nurse and the accuracy rate was 72.1% ($n=132$) for experimental group and 67.3% ($n= 124$) for the control group. However, a Fisher Exact Test was conducted and was not found statistically significant. The experimental group had a higher accuracy rating than the control group that didn't have to do a project. Though only the experimental group was mandated to participate in the online discussions, both groups took part in it. Therefore, the researchers concluded that both groups enjoyed talking to their peers about triage. Overall, the study concluded that online training for triage was successful since the majority of the participants liked learning it. The nurses were able to transfer the knowledge gained from the online training into clinical practice with a great percentage of accuracy.

Benefits of an Electronic Self-Learning Module

Electric learning modules provide an effective teaching platform with multiple benefits: (a) cost efficiency, (b) convenience, and (c) enhancement cognitive skills. An on-ground training class, which needs an instructor, classroom preparation, learning

materials, and travel expenses, can become costly when compared to an ELM (Andriotis, 2018; Ghirardini, 2011). Secondly, the ELM offers learners the convenience of working at their own pace and in their preferred environment where they are free to make mistakes without being judged by peers or teachers (Andriotis, 2018; Ghirardini, 2011; Xu, 2016). The ELM also is able to reach a wider target audience by engaging learners who find it difficult to attend conventional classroom sessions (Ghirardini, 2011; Xu, 2016). Lastly, the benefit of an ELM is that it helps to build cognitive skills by stimulating thinking through its interactive style (Ghirardini, 2011). A medical-based ELM can be used provide knowledge and foster comprehension on a variety of diagnosis, pathophysiological concepts, diagrams, flow-charts, and pictures as well as video clips on procedural skills needed for applying insight and problem-solving skills for the learner (Ghirardini, 2011). The interactive part of the ELM allows learners to take an active role in their learning process by interacting with the content to improve their understanding (Andriotis, 2018; Ghirardini, 2011). In a study conducted by Millor et al. (2015), 175 medical radiology students who used a clicker while engaged in an interactive learning module preferred it over traditional classroom teaching. The interactive learning module engaged the students to be active participants who were motivated to learn, leading to higher retention of information, improving long-term retention, and achieving better learning outcomes.

According to the E-learning methodologies guide, there are factors that are beneficial to the learner as well as factors that are a must in order to be able to utilize the training module (Ghirardini, 2011). The benefit with this specific learning module is that it is a self-study. Learners can take their time to study the material and understand the

concepts and have the opportunity to go back to review sections they did not understand (Ghirardini, 2011; Xu, 2016). However, the “must” criteria is that learners must have computers and high-speed internet access (Xu, 2016). Learners also must be computer literate and able to follow simple commands in order to navigate through the sessions (Ghirardini, 2011). Learners must also (a) be self-motivated, (b) be able to go into self-study mode, and (c) be able to pace themselves.

Creating an Electronic Self-Learning Module

There are many different ways an e-learning module can be created. Research was conducted to find guidelines for creating PowerPoint slides. The rules for PowerPoint teaching presentations consist of (Andriotis, 2018; Goodwill Community Foundation Global [GCF], 2018):

- Know your audience in order to create a presentation appropriate for their learning needs.
- Keep text and fonts simple and easy to read; do not overwhelm your audience.
- Use animations cautiously; too much can become a distraction to the learner.
- Use large, simple fonts and theme colors.

A learning module can be student-centered, which means an educational module can be created with only the student in mind and not be a curriculum-based learning module (Xu, 2016). The content details are specifically selected with a course plan, course materials, discussion topics, and interactive activities to engage in an active learning process (Andriotis, 2018; Ghirardini, 2011; Xu, 2016). The interactive learning module helps learners strengthen their critical thinking skills while gaining new knowledge and insight (Andriotis, 2018).

METHODS

The method section provides a detailed description of the planned execution of this quality improvement doctoral project. It consists of (a) the design, (b) setting, (c) participants, (d) patient data, (e) educational content, and (f) instruments used to complete the project. The potential implementation of the plan, including data collection, analysis, and evaluation for the project, are disclosed. Ethical considerations are discussed.

Design

This doctorate in nursing practice (DNP) QI project is a pre- and post-design to implement and evaluate a new ED triage standard protocols to improve front-end ED throughput by training triage nurses using the ELM. Primary measurable outcomes are the ED metrics of DTD, DTA, DTDC, and LWBS after the triage nurses have received training with the ELM for using the new SP. The overall goal is to improve ED throughput and to alleviate ED overcrowding by changing the triage process.

The current *Standardized Protocol: Treatment and Diagnostic Protocol Policy* (Appendix C) was a policy created by the project hospital's ED physician. It was a set of predetermined orders with strict guidelines utilized by the triage nurse to order diagnostic tests and initiate simple medical treatments prior to the patient being evaluated by the ED physician. The order set selected was determined by the patient's chief complaint, and the presenting signs and symptoms. A nurse was to use clinical judgment along with the order set to determine a course of treatment for the patient. The goal of the SP was to help expedite patients' care while they are waiting for a bed in the ED treatment area.

This early initiation of diagnostic testing allowed for results to be available by the time the patient was taken to the treatment area to see the ED physician.

Setting

The project will take place at a small, 11-bed ED, intercommunity hospital located in Southern California. The acute care hospital has 140 beds. The hospital is able to provide an ED, intensive care unit (ICU), operating room (OR) services, medical-surgical, telemetry, inpatient psychiatric care, and obstetric (OB) services. The hospital is not a stroke or cardiac receiving center. The ED is certified as an Emergency Department Pediatric Approved (EDAP) center, however pediatric patients are not admitted to the hospital since there is no pediatric unit.

The ED has processed approximately 2,000 patients monthly for a variety of complaints, from abdominal pain, chest pain, and respiratory problems to orthopedic injuries. Patients arrived to the ED by ambulance or by walking in. There has been only one ED physician on duty at all times. There have been no mid-level healthcare providers staffed in ED.

Participants

The participants will consist of 22 ED triage RNs. Currently there are 18 triage nurses and four triage charge nurses. Among the 18 triage nurses, there are 12 full-time and six per-diem nurses. Among the triage charge nurses, all four are full-time. All the nurses have worked at the project hospital from six months to 25 years. There are 11 triage nurses with more than five years of nursing experience and 11 triage nurses with less than one year of nursing experience.

Inclusion Criteria

All designated triage nurses will be included in the ELM training.

Exclusion Criteria

No triage nurse will be excluded from the ELM. The triage nurses cannot opt out of participating since this is a department process change. The triage nurses can opt out of completing the pre- and post-SP survey.

Patient Data

Once implementation of the QI project commences, pre-patient data will be extracted retrospectively prior to implementation of the SP. Data will be analyzed to determine the ED metrics. Post-patient data will be collected after implementation of the SP. Patient data will consist of adult patients entering the ED seeking medical treatment at the project hospital. There will be no direct patient contact since all data will be extracted from the electronic medical record (EMR). All patient data will be de-identified.

Inclusion

Included will be all adult patients (>18 years old) admitted, discharged, or left without being seen from the ED.

Exclusions

Patients who expired during the course of treatment while in the ED, pediatric patients (<18 years old), and psychiatric patients waiting for psychiatric evaluations will not be included in the project.

Ethics and Human Subjects Protection

The project investigator obtained a signed consent letter from the chief nursing

officer of the project hospital, granting permission to conduct the DNP QI project (Appendix D). IRB approval was obtained from California State University, Los Angeles (Appendix E). There are no foreseeable risks to patients since no actual patients will be directly evaluated. All data will be aggregated and de-identified. The investigator will apply all safety measures to maintain confidentiality and protect the project hospital's identifying information.

Educational Content

The project investigator (PI) developed an electronic self-learning module to teach the triage nurses on how to use the ED's new SP. The PowerPoint ELM was titled: *Emergency Department Standardized Procedure: A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage* (Appendix F). Prior to the development of the ELM, extensive research was conducted to learn about developing an educational training module. A review of the literature was conducted on how to make an effective PowerPoint slide presentation to determine the most effective teaching modalities for an informative training session.

The ELM training will be available to the nurses for six weeks in order to give them enough time to be able to do the module. The goal of the course is that the triage nurses will be able to understand and independently initiate appropriate ED order-sets and follow simple treatment guidelines for triaged patients.

The importance of the ELM is that it contains the order sets, which are evidence-based practice guidelines for common chief complaints and signs and symptoms of patients presenting to the ED. The module contains (a) the course purpose, (b) learning objectives, and (c) presentation of the new ED SP guidelines. It has provided the definition as well as pathophysiology of the chief complaints. It is vital that the triage

nurses understand the basic concepts behind these specific conditions in order to choose the appropriate SP order set for the patients.

After the ELM was created, a mini-pilot of the presentation was conducted with two nursing educators who were certified in nursing professional development by the American Nurses Credentialing Center. The PI developed an evaluation/critique tool for the ELM and provided it to the two nurse educators (Appendix G). The evaluators were asked to time themselves to see how long the module took to complete and to provide two points each regarding what they liked and what they thought needed improvement. The results of the evaluation were positive with comments like “a lot of information for the nurse to understand the triage process.” Both educators stated they liked the ELM. One wrote, “I learned about physiology about disease processes” and “Easy to follow.” Adjustments were made based on their suggestions for wording and rephrasing some slides, as well as adding a note to explain why these topics were chosen.

It should be noted that an overview of the BRN guidelines to become a continuing education (CE) provider was also done in order to be qualified to provide the learner with CE hours upon completion of the training module. A detailed guideline on becoming a CE provider is discussed in the next paragraphs. Upon approval, the PI will be able to provide the learner with 1.8 CE hours for completion of the course.

Continuing Education Provider

In order to ensure RNs are continuing to enhance their knowledge, the BRN has required that RNs take approved continuing education classes (total 30 contact hours) every two years with the renewal of their license. According to the California Code of Regulations, continuing education is defined by as “variety of forms of learning

experiences, including, but not limited to, lectures, conferences, academic studies, in-service education, institutes, seminars, workshops, extension studies, and independent/home study programs undertaken by registered nurses for re-licensure” (16 CA ADC § 1450).

Board of Registered Nurses Requirements

All contents described below follows the criteria established for BRN Professional and Vocational Regulations for Continued Education under Title 16, Division 14, and Article 5 for continuing education which can be found at govt.westlaw.com. A continuing education provider application (Appendix H) was submitted to BRN to be able to provide contact hours of 1.8 hours for the educational electronic learning module.

The Course

The e-learning module proposed is an electronic self-learning module (ELM) for triage nurses or other healthcare professionals in a small, local Orange County intercommunity hospital who are interested in learning about an emergency department standardized procedure. This module meets the criteria for the BRN continuing education courses since it is relevant for the practice of nursing and was created to improve the skills and scientific knowledge for a triage nurse providing direct patient care. All categories were chief complaints acquired from a local emergency department’s *Standardized Procedure: Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol* (only those categories used in the standard procedure will be addressed).

Course goal and objectives. The course goal has been to provide the triage nurse a clinical approach to accurately and efficiently diagnose common chief complaints

in an emergency department. Information presented was organized in a problem-solving process that included: (a) chief complaint, (b) definition, (c) symptoms, (d) pathophysiology, (e) physical findings, (f) diagnostic studies, and (g) possible diagnosis.

Upon completion of this module, the learner should be able to:

- Explain the purpose of this learning module
- Discuss the four categories of the patient interview
- Differentiate between subjective and objective findings
- Discuss key elements of the physical examination
- State the seven categories of the problem-solving process
- Explain the problem-solving process of two different presenting chief complaints

In writing the e-learning module course objectives, Bloom's taxonomy was utilized. Bloom's taxonomy is a hierarchical model used in education for measuring learning outcomes according to six cognitive levels that have been associated with how the brain processes information and thought (Armstrong, n.d.; Education Reform, 2014; TeAchnology, 2018). The six levels (from simplest to most complex) are: (a) remembering, (b) understanding, (c) applying, (d) analyzing, (e) evaluating, and (f) creating (Education Reform, 2014). Each level has subcategories consisting of "action words" corresponding to the cognitive process associated with the learning level (Education Reform, 2014). For example, at the "understanding" level, the learner is able to "explain" information; at the "evaluating" level, the learner can "critique" (Armstrong, n.d.). The use of Bloom's Taxonomy in writing learning objectives gives the instructor a framework to organize teaching objectives such as "plan and deliver appropriate

instructions, design valid assessment tasks and strategies, and ensure that instruction and assessments are aligned with the objectives” (Armstrong, n.d., p. 3).

Purpose. The purpose of the learning module has been to help the triage nurse with a clinical approach to accurately and efficiently diagnose common chief complaints. A second purpose was to help the triage nurse understand the thinking process and problem solving that goes along with assessment of patients presenting to the emergency department.

Course content. The learner will be presented with the purpose of the learning module along with a “Patient Interview” PowerPoint slide that detailed the information that needed to be gathered from the patient upon triage. Another slide has provided pertinent information on the physical examination and explained subjective versus objective findings. A copy of the “Standardized Procedure: Treatment and Diagnostic Protocol” (2018) has been provided on one slide so the learner could become familiar with it. Following this was the core of the teachings where each of 15 chief complaint categories are presented and organized in a problem-solving process that included seven criteria: (a) chief complaint, (b) definition, (c) symptoms, (d) pathophysiology, (e) physical findings, (f) diagnostic studies, and (g) possible diagnosis. Quizzes to emphasize key points have been placed sporadically throughout the learning module. A pre-and post-test was given to evaluate learner comprehension. A course evaluation survey will be given to the learner upon completion of the learning module.

The course content of the e-learning module was presented to two nurse educators who were certified in nursing professional development through the American Nurses Credentialing Center’s Commission on Accreditation (ANCC) for their review of written

materials for (a) clarity of subject content and course structure, (b) timing and length of the course, and (c) the feasibility of the program and its accessibility. All feedback was incorporated and improvements were made as necessary.

Aside from the necessary core course content, the ELM PowerPoint also included quizzes that consisted of multiple choice with only one correct answer for each question (Ghirardini, 2011) and true or false questions (Ghirardini, 2011). Quizzes are used during transitioning of data subjects and are a good method to reinforce the learning of the content presented. It allows learners to have a break from course content, while keeping their attention to build the knowledge and the skills needed to transfer principles and procedures over to the actual job performance. A course outline is provided on Table 2.

Course evaluations. The course evaluation for this learning module will provide a method to verify that the module was completed. The triage nurses taking the course will evaluate it according to the following criteria: (a) whether the course contents met the course objectives; (b) whether the instructor provided sufficient content to teach the subject; and (c) whether the teaching method was appropriate. Evaluation methods also consisted of quizzes placed within the module, and a pre-test and post-test.

Requirements/Hours. According to California Code of Regulations (2018), calculation of continuing education hours (16 CA ADC § 1455) are based on the number of lecture instructions per minute. For continued nursing education (CNE), 50 minutes of instruction is equal to one contact hour. This learning module is 1.5 hours or 90 minutes lecture, making it 1.8 contact hours.

Table 2

Course Outline for ELM: Emergency Department Standardized Procedure: A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage

Course Topic	Course Contents	
Course Pre-Test Course Objectives Purpose		
Patient Interview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chief complaint • Vital Signs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Symptoms • Medical History
Physical Examination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vital Signs • Height & Weight • Quick Focused Assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subjective Findings • Objective Findings • Use Interview style questions
Sample Standard Procedure Policy		
Problem-Solving Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chief complaint • Definition • Symptoms • Pathophysiology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Findings • Diagnostic Studies • Possible Diagnosis
Chief Complaints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaphylaxis with Hypotension/ Unstable Airway • Symptomatic Hypotension • Chest Pain • Elevated Temperature/ Fever • Wheezing with Respiratory Distress • Seizures • Vaginal Bleeding • Abdominal Pain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak/Dizzy and > 60 years of age • GI bleeding • Urinary Tract Infection • Lacerations with Possibility of Foreign Bodies • Overdose • Fractures and Sprains • Head Injury (Traumatic)
Conclusion Course Posttest Course Evaluation		

Note. Quizzes are placed throughout the course.

Proof of attendance/Certification. Students will be provided a certification of completion, documenting they have successfully completed the learning module. Information on the certificate contains all information listed in 16 CA ADC § 1458. The certificate of completion will be issued to attendees within 90 days after the conclusion of the course (Appendix I).

Instructor qualifications. The qualifications for this instructor (16 CA ADC § 1457) for the course are: (a) is a registered nurse, (b) holds a doctorate in nursing practice from the CSU Consortium program, and (c) has current and 17 years of experience in the content area. A copy of the instructor's curriculum vitae is kept along with all records and is available upon BRN's request.

Advertisement. A flyer (Appendix J)) will be distributed via email to all qualifying ED triage nurses. A flyer also will be displayed in the emergency department break room. Announcements regarding the course will be given during the ED staff meeting. Verbal reminders to triage nurses will be given by the ED director and charge nurse during shift reports. The flyer will include information noted in 16 CA ADC § 1459, specifically: "Provider approved by the California Board of Registered Nursing, Provider Number _____, for _____ contact hours". A clear, concise description of the course content, objectives will be written on the flyer, as will the provider's name as officially recorded on file with the BRN.

Record Keeping. Records of the course outline, dates, and student names for the e-learning module will be securely logged electronically (16 CA ADC § 1458) (Appendix K). All participants' names with their RN license numbers, along with a record of the

certificates of completion issued, are to be kept for five years by the instructor and hospital department office in the local intercommunity hospital.

Provider policies. The provider policy (16 CA ADC § 1454) will be made available upon request to the learner. Since this is a mandatory e-learning module, there is no costs involved for the learner. Registration is completed upon logging in to take the module via hospital email and assigned learning module. Only registered triage nurses will be assigned the learning module. The nurses are allowed to stay after or come before their shift to complete the module and will be credited two hours of pay upon completion of the course.

Audits of providers. The BRN has the authority to audit all records, courses, instructors at any time (16 CA ADC § 1454).

Instruments

Nursing Survey

The triage nurses will be given the *Standard Procedure Pre-Intervention Survey* (Appendix L) to rate their thoughts and attitudes about having a SP for triage. This tool also has questions about the use of the protocol. The survey consists of a few demographic questions and 10 Likert scale questions pertaining to how they felt about using a SP in triage. The last part of the survey consists of three open-ended questions regarding the SP. At the end of the project the *Standard Procedure Post-Intervention Survey* (Appendix L) will be provided. It has the same pre-survey questions with the addition of Likert questions and open-ended questions that relate to (a) what they considered was the feasibility of using the SP, (b) how the nurses liked using a SP, and (c) what recommendations they had for improvement. All surveys will be sent to the

triage nurses. The triage nurses will print out and complete the survey and anonymously place the survey in the investigator's mailbox. The survey results will help in formatting future educational programs for teaching or reinforcing knowledge regarding the SP.

Standard Protocol Policy

The project hospital had an SP Policy that was confusing, lengthy, and rarely if ever utilized. Therefore, it was brought to the ED throughput physician chair's attention. Since then, a new SP for triage was created. The new SP policy is considered to be improved because it is shorter, more succinct, and clearer. The new SP policy will be emailed to all triage nurses along with the ELM. The SP policy will also be laminated and placed in the triage booth for easy access to be used as a reference guide.

ELM Training

The ELM will be a mandatory training requirement for all triage nurses. Further details on this training module can be found in the "Do" section of the implementation plan for the new triage policy as well as in the BRN requirement for CE provider section (Appendix H).

The e-learning module pre- and post-tests. The pre- and post-tests have been embedded within the PowerPoint (Appendix F). The tests consist of the same five questions that help evaluate the learner's knowledge before and after completing the educational module.

Course evaluation. The course evaluation is embedded at the end of the educational module. It consists of seven questions designed to determine what the learner thought of the course (Appendix F).

POTENTIAL IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The objective for this DNP QI project is to implement a new SP in order to expedite patients through the ED. The project process will follow the plan-do-study-action (PDSA) framework.

Plan

The plan for this project will be the improvement of ED throughput by implementing and evaluating a new SP for triage. The participants have been identified as 18 triage nurses and 4 charge nurses. The buy-in from the stakeholders (the chief nursing officer [CNO], ED director, ED physicians) is a vital component to any change in the project hospital. The implementation will begin with educating all the triage nurses with the ELM.

Time Frame and Plan to Implement

It is upon the discretion of the ED Director to finalize the dates of implementation of the new SP for triage. The project investigator has already received the necessary approvals from the hospital administration (CNO) and the Internal Review Board (IRB). Disclosure of the innovative project to all staff has been done using various methods of communication such as ED staff meetings, emails, flyers, and verbal face-to-face awareness. An information letter to participants (Appendix M) will be sent out to all the triage nurses explaining the doctoral project for the new triage SP and the nursing surveys to be conducted. Retrospective patient data will be requested for six months prior to the initiation of the project (January 2019 to July 2019). The ED triage nurses will be trained for six weeks on the ELM and will also receive hands-on training on actual triage patients. The time frame for the innovative project is six months. The projected

implementation for the triage nurse training date is estimated to be in July 2019. Once training is completed, the new SP will be initiated in mid-August 2019 until February 2020. Data will again be gathered for this time period, for a total of six months of data collection.

Literature Review

A review of literature has been completed to identify relevant, current guidelines and evidence-based research to learn of the many different aspects of improving ED throughput using a SP for triage. The literature review has also been conducted for creating an electronic PowerPoint educational module as well as requirements for becoming a continuing education provider through the BRN.

Standardized Protocol

The project hospital's SP was re-written, and the new SP has been approved by the governing board on March 2018.

Do

Electronic Self-Learning Module

Once started, the ELM will be offered over six weeks to allow sufficient time for all the triage nurses to be trained. The ELM will be emailed to the triage nurses to complete. The ED nurses will have the flexibility to take the online training before or after their work shifts and be discouraged from taking it during their shift. They will be paid up to two hours to complete the module. In order to meet the educational requirements, the ELM needs to be completed before the triage nurse can proceed to the hands-on component of the SP training in the triage area. Using the electronic log, the PI will keep track of all triage nurses who complete the ELM.

Triage Hands-On Training

After completion of the ELM, the project investigator (PI) will provide a two-week mentoring session for the triage nurses to perform the hands-on training using the new SP. The PI will be present to supervise, answer questions, and provide support for the triage nurses. If the PI is not available, the charge nurse will be the resource person available for the triage nurses.

The New Triage Process

When a patient arrives to the ED, the triage nurse will perform an assessment of the patient. The patient then will be categorized by priority, according to the hospital's triage policy derived from a triage tool called Emergency Severity Index (ESI) 5-Level Triage System (Gilboy, Tanabe, Travers, & Rosenau, 2011). This triage system requires the triage nurse to utilize critical thinking and clinical judgement to identify which patients need immediate attention and which patients can wait. The ESI is a reliable and valid tool used by the triage nurse (Buschhorn, Strout, Sholl, & Baumann, 2013). The ESI helps the nurse prioritize patients based on their complaints and the severity of their presenting symptoms, so they will be assigned to the correct patient waiting area (Dateo, 2013; Gilboy et al., 2011; O'Connor et al., 2014; Stanfield, 2015).

For those patients who are safe to wait in the waiting room for an available bed, the triage nurse will initiate treatment by referring to the SP guidelines and order-sets. The triage nurse will determine which potential diagnostic tests need to be ordered or medications that need to be administered while the patient is waiting to be seen by the ED physician. Laboratory technicians can be called to assist with blood draws. When

patients are finally brought back to the main ED treatment area, they should have the test results available for the physician to read. This process decreases the total wait time for patients in the ED, therefore improving ED metrics. It is a more efficient and cost-effective process and would help increase patient satisfaction. Figure 5 shows the diagram of the triage process.

Data Collection

The PI had requested retrospective de-identified ED metrics from ED director for all triaged patients during the months of July 2017 to December 2017 in order to compare the patient throughput times from the pre-implementation of the ELM and SP to the post-implementation of the ELM and SP. Unfortunately, the PI was not given the data as requested. Once the ED director has set a date for the project initiation, the project investigator will again attempt to gather pre-project implementation data from the previous six months regarding patient throughput. Data will also be collected from all the nursing surveys, the ELM pre- and post-tests, and course evaluations.

Study

Anticipated data collection and analysis of ED throughput and hospital's ED metrics would be displayed in this section. This section would also include the evaluation of the process and comparing of results pre- and post-implementation of the training and use of the SP.

Data Analysis

Retrospective data and post- implementation data will consist of the following:

- All data collected will be aggregated and de-identified

- Data collection will consist of daily patient census, DTD, DTA, DTDC, and LWBS rates
- There will be summary statistics of all outcome measures and a comparison of ED throughput times pre-implementation and post-implementation.

Nursing Surveys, Pre- and Post-Tests, and Evaluation

Analyzing data from the triage pre- and post-implementation survey is to gain insight on the triage nurses' attitudes regarding using the SP. The post-survey will also inquire about the feasibility of using the SP. Demographics, years of nursing experience, and triage experience will also be evaluated.

The analysis of the pre- and post-test within the ELM would allow the PI to evaluate if knowledge was acquired.

The course evaluation would provide an analysis of what the triage nurses thought of the e-learning module, of its feasibility, if the contents met the learning objectives, and how they liked it.

Statistical Analysis

The PI will use an Excel spreadsheet to compute and organize all data received. Statistical analysis used will be:

- *t* test for comparison of the pre- and post-surveys
- Mean averages to summarize the nursing survey

Evaluate the Process

At the end of the DNP QI project, recommendations for modifications and improvements in the triage process will be proposed to the leadership team. The recommendations will be developed in collaboration with the triage nurses.

Summary

A summary of what was learned would also be disclosed.

Act

The last cycle in the PDSA is to act on the results: whether it will be to change the current process and adopt the ELM and SP, modify it, or abandon it altogether. The results will determine if the PDSA cycle needs to be repeated or modified in any way. If the results are positive, then the QI project will be implemented as a permanent process for triage at the project hospital.

RESULTS

The implementation for the SP for triage has not yet commenced for the project hospital. The emergency director will need to finalize the project start date. All data collected regarding ED metrics, throughput times, and nursing attitudes for the SP will be shared with the stakeholders and ED nurses when available. The anticipated results are that the use of the new SP in triage will help improve ED throughput metrics. The key for accurate triaging is appropriate training for the triage nurses in the process of triage along with the use of the SP.

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE IN NURSING

Potentially, this innovative project of utilizing a SP can be implemented and incorporated into any ED's triage process. It is anticipated that the project will provide evidence-based data showing the benefits of implementing a SP in an ED's triage. However, the effectiveness of using a SP depends mainly on the triage nurses who are carrying it out. Therefore, it is imperative that the triage nurses receive adequate training. The ELM created can be a great resource and learning tool. It equips the triage nurses by guiding them in their decision making and helps nurses make the critical judgements needed to approach a patient's symptomatology and chief complaints in an organized, systematic, problem-solving approach. Together, both interventions could help provide the best, most efficient patient care and should help improve any hospital's ED throughput and ED metrics.

RECOMMENDATIONS

At the end of the DNP QI project, any recommendations for modifications and improvements in the triage process will be proposed to the leadership team. The hope is that this QI project will provide substantial evidence that the initiation and usage of the new SP helped not only reinforce effective triaging, but also expedited patient flow and throughput in the ED.

Recommendations for the ELM will also be taken into consideration for improvement of the training session. The data collected from the triage nurses will be a valuable critique of the ELM. Data can further direct the usefulness of the module and provide information for its improvement. Possible recommendations might be to (a) make the learning module shorter, (b) create flow charts, (c) provide more interactive contents, (d) break apart the learning material, or (e) create a voice-over of the slides if it contained too much information. Other recommendations may be to create an on-ground workshop instead of an online module.

SUMMARY

ED overcrowding is a known problem nationwide with negative consequences. Initiating an evidenced-based standard protocol in triage can expedite the patient care process and help improve ED metrics and ED throughput for this small intercommunity hospital. Therefore, it is important to adequately train the nurses to understand the process and equip them with the skills and tools needed to approach their patients' symptomology and chief complaints. The development of an electronic self-learning module by the project investigator will provide an education that is presented in an organized, problem-solving process to guide the triage nurse to possible diagnosis and treatment options.

With the use of the teaching module, in an attempt to change an organization, it is important to start on a small scale with periods of evaluation before moving forward to the next steps. This plan-do-study-act framework will allow the project hospital to initiate the change of using the new "Standardized Procedure: Treatment and Diagnostic Protocol Policy" (2018) in triage. The application of the evidence-based standardized procedures will accelerate the patient care experience while providing best practices.

Follow-up for this innovative project requires the PI to analyze whether the triage training had improved ED throughput times along with all the ED metrics by collecting SP pre-implementation and post-implementation ED throughput times. As the triage nurses become more comfortable with the SP, and hopefully, ED throughput improves, the institution can continue to improve the ED by seeing if use of the SP has improved the times of the ED-admitted patients to their inpatient rooms. The goal is to deliver the

most effective, efficient, and safe quality care for optimal patient outcomes for all ED patients.

REFERENCES

- American College of Emergency Physicians [ACEP]. (2016). *Emergency department overcrowding: High impact solutions*. [Task force report]. Retrieved from https://www.acep.org/globalassets/sites/acep/media/crowding/empc_crowding-ip_092016.pdf
- American Heart Association [AHA] (1999). *ACC/AHA guidelines for the management of patients with acute myocardial infarction: Executive summary and recommendations*. [Practice guidelines]. Retrieved from <http://circ.ahajournals.org/content/circulationaha/100/9/1016.full.pdf>
- Andriotis, N. (2018). *How to develop a highly interactive online training program*. Retrieved from the TalentLMS website: <https://www.talentlms.com/blog/how-create-interactive-online-training-program/>
- Armstrong, P. (n.d.) *Bloom's Taxonomy*. Retrieved from the Vanderbilt University Center for Teaching website: <https://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/blooms-taxonomy/>
- Bakhsh, A. (2015, December 5). *Crowding in the emergency department: Strategies to end it* [Web log comment]. Retrieved from the emDocs website: <http://www/emdocs.net/edcrowding/>
- Begaz, T., Elashoff, D., Grogan, T. R., Talan, D., & Taira, B. R. (2016). Initiating diagnostic studies on patients with abdominal pain in the waiting room decreases time spent in an emergency department bed: A randomized controlled trial. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 69(3), 298-307. doi: 10.1016/j.annemergmed.2016.06.040

- Betz, M., Stempien, J., Trivedi, S., & Bryce, S. (2016). A determination of emergency department pre-triage times in patients not arriving by ambulance compared to widely used guideline recommendations. *Canadian Journal of Emergency Medicine (CJEM)*, 19(4), 265-270. doi:10.1017/cem.2016.398
- Buttigieg, S. C., Dey, P. K., & Cassar, M. R. (2015). Combined quality function deployment and logical framework analysis to improve quality of emergency care in Malta. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*, 29(2), 123-140. doi:10.1108/IJHCQA-04-2014-0040
- Buschhorn, H. M., Strout, T. D., Sholl, J. M., & Baumann, M. R. (2013). Emergency medical services triage using the Emergency Severity Index: Is it reliable and valid? *Journal of Emergency Nursing [JEN]*, 39(5), 55-63. doi: org/10.1016/j.jen.2011.11.003.
- Cabilan, C. J., & Boyde, M. (2017). A systematic review of the impact of nurse-initiated medications in the emergency department. *Australian Emergency Nursing Journal*, 2017(20), 53-62. doi.org/10.1016/j.aenj.2017.04.001
- California Health Care Almanac [CHCA]. (2018). *California emergency departments: Use grows as coverage expands*. Retrieved from <https://www.chcf.org/wpcontent/uploads/2018/08/CAEmergencyDepartments2018.pdf>
- Canadian Association of Emergency Physicians [CAEP]. (2018). *Emergency department overcrowding*. Retrieved from <http://caep.ca/advocacy/romanowcommission/EmergencydepartmentovercrowdingCertification/QAPI/downloads/PDSA.Cycledebedits.pdf>

- Chan, T.C., Killeen, J. P., Kelly, D., Guss, D. A. (2005). Impact of rapid entry and accelerated care at triage on reducing emergency department patient wait times, lengths of stay, and rate of left without being seen. *Annals of Emergency Medicine* [AEM], 46(6), 491-497. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2005.06.013
- Chow, J. L., Niedzwiecki, M., J., & Hsia, R., Y. (2017). Trends in the supply of California's emergency departments and inpatient services, 2005-2014: A retrospective analysis. *British Medical Journal (BMJ)*, 2017(7). 1-8. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-014721
- Continuing Education Advertisement. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1459 (2019).
- Continuing Education Approved Providers. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1454 (2019).
- Continuing Education Courses. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1456 (2019).
- Continuing Education Hours. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1455 (2019).
- Continuing Education Course Verification. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1458 (2019).
- Continuing Education Definitions. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1450 (2019).
- Continuing Education Instructor Qualifications. 16 CCR, 16 CA ADC § 1457 (2019).
- Cooper, J. J., Datner, E. M., & Pines, J. M. (2008). Effect of an automated chest radiograph at triage protocol on time to antibiotics in patients admitted with pneumonia. *American Journal of Emergency Medicine* (AJEM), 2008(26), 264-269. doi:10.1016/j.ajem.2007.05.008
- Dateo, J. (2013). What factors increase the accuracy and inter-rater reliability of the Emergency Severity Index among emergency nurses in triaging adult patients? *Journal of Emergency Nursing* [JEN], 39(2), 203-207. doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2011.09.002

- Domangal, S. E. & Vets, J. (2015). Emergency nursing triage: Keeping it safe. *Clinical* 41(4), 313-316. doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2015.01.022
- Douma, M.J., Drake, C. A., O'Dochartaigh, D., & Smith, K. E. (2016). A pragmatic randomized evaluation of a nurse-initiated protocol to improve timeliness of care in an urban emergency department. *American College of Emergency Physicians (ACEP)*, 68(5), 546-552. doi.org/10.1016/j.annemergmed.2016.06.019
- Ebrahimi, M., Mirhaghi, A., Mazlom, R., Heydari, A., Nassehi, A., & Jafari, M. (2016). The role descriptions of triage nurse in emergency department: A Delphi study. *Scientifica*, (2016), 1-7. doi: 10.1155/2016/5269815
- The Glossary of Education Reform. (2014). *Bloom's taxonomy*. Retrieved from Great Schools Partnership website: <https://www.edglossary.org/blooms-taxonomy/>
- ProPublica. (2017). *ER Wait Watcher: Project Hospital*. Retrieved from <https://projects.propublica.org/emergency/hospital/050580>
- Fee, C., Weber, E. J., Maak, C. A., & Bacchetti, P. (2007). Effect of emergency department crowding on time to antibiotics in patients admitted with community-acquired pneumonia. *Annals of Emergency Medicine [AEM]*, 50(5), 501-509. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2007.08.003
- Franklin, A. E., Gubrud-Howe, P., Sideras, S., & Lee, C. S. (2015). Effectiveness of simulation preparation on novice nurses' competence and self-efficacy in a multiple-patient simulation. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 36(5) 324-325. doi:10.5480/14-1546

- Ghirardini, B. (2011). *E-learning methodologies: A guide for designing and developing e-learning courses*. Retrieved from Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations website: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/015/i2516e/i2516e.pdf>
- Gilboy N, Tanabe T, Travers D, & Rosenau A. M. (2011). *Emergency Severity Index (ESI): A triage tool for emergency department care. Implementation handbook (2012 ed.)*, 1-114. Retrieved from the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) website: <https://www.ahrq.gov/professionals/systems/hospital/esi/index.html>
- Goodwill Community Foundation Global [GCF]. (2018). *Simple rules for better PowerPoint presentations*. Retrieved from <https://edu.gcfglobal.org/en/powerpoint-tips/simple-rules-for-better-powerpoint-presentations/1/>
- Goulding, L., Parke, H., Maharaj, R., Loveridge, R., McLoone, A., Hadfield, S., Helme, E., . . . Sandall, J. (2015). Improving critical care discharge summaries: a collaborative quality improvement project using PDSA. *British Medical Journal Quality Improvement Reports*, 2015(4), 1-8. doi:10.1136/bmjquality.u203938.w3268
- Hanna, T. N., Rohatgi, S., Shekhani, H., I. A., & Johnson, J. (2016). Clinical information available during emergency department imaging order entry and radiologist interpretation. *Emergency Radiology*, 24, 361-367. doi.10.1007/s10140-0171488-4
- Houston, C., Sanchez, L.D., Fischer, C., Volz, K., Wolfe, R. (2015). Waiting for triage: Unmeasured time in patient flow. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 16(1), 39-42. doi: 10.5811/westjem.2014.11.22824

- Hwang, C., Payton, T., Weeks, E., & Plourde, M. (2016). Implementing triage standing orders in the emergency department leads to reduced physician-to-disposition times. *Advances in Emergency Medicine, 2016*, 1-7. doi.org/10.1155/2016/7213625
- Ignatavicius, D. D., Workman L. M., & Rebar C. R. (2018). *Medical-surgical nursing: Concepts for interprofessional collaborative care* (9th ed.). St. Louis, MO: Elsevier
- Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (2018). Science of improvement: Testing changes. Retrieved from <http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/ScienceofImprovementTestingChanges.aspx>
- Khasawneh, R., Simonsen, K., Snowden, J., Higgins, J., & Beck., G. (2016). The effectiveness of e-learning in pediatric medical student education. *Medical Education Online, 21*, 1-3. doi: org/10.3402/meo.v21.29516
- Lee, W. W., Filiatrault, L., Abu-Laban, R. B., Rashidi, A., Yau, L., & Liu, N. (2016). Effect of triage nurse-initiated radiography using the Ottawa Ankle Rules on emergency department length of stay at a tertiary centre. *Canadian Journal of Emergency Medicine [CJEM], 18(2)*, 90-98. doi: 10.1017/cem.2015.67
- Lindley-Jones, M., & Finlayson, B. J. (2000). Triage nurse requested x-rays – Are they worthwhile? *Journal of Accident Emergency Medicine, 17*, 103-107. doi: 10.1136/emj.17.2.10
- Marcel, D. (2017). OneSearch allows researchers statewide access to CSU library collections. *Daily Titan: The Student Voice of Cal State Fullerton*. Retrieved from <https://dailytitan.com/2017/10/onesearch-allows-researchers-statewide-access-to-csu-library-collections/>

- Millor, M., Etxano, J., Slon P., García-Barquín, P., Villanueva, A., Bastarrika, G., & Pueyo, J. (2015). Use of remote response devices: an effective interactive method in the long- term learning. *European Society of Radiology*, 25(1), 894-900. doi.10.1007/s00330-014-3468-3
- Moen, R. & Norman, C. (2010, November). *Circling back: Clearing the myths about the Deming cycle and seeing how it keeps evolving*. Retrieved from the Associates in Process Improvement website: <http://www.apiweb.org/circling-back.pdf>
- O'Connor, E., Gatien, M., Weir, C., & Calder, L. (2014, April). Evaluating the effect of emergency department crowding on triage destination. *International Journal of Emergency Medicine [IJEM]*, 7(16). doi: 10.1186/1865-1380-7-16
- Office of Statewide Health Planning and Development. [OSHPD]. (2014-2016). *Emergency Department Summary Reports, by facility [Data file]*. Retrieved from <http://www.oshpd.ca.gov/HID/MIRCal/EDASManual.html>
- Parrish, M. (2016). Toward transformation: Digital tools for online dance pedagogy. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 117(3), 168-182. doi: 10.1080/10632913.2016.1187974
- Pines, J. M. & Hollander, J. E. (2009). The association between emergency department crowding and adverse cardiovascular outcomes in patients with chest pains. *Annals Emergency Medicine*, 16(7), 617-625. doi: 10.1111/j.1553-2712.2009.00456
- Qazi, K., Altimimi, S., Tamim, H., & Serrano K. (2010). Impact of an emergency nurse–initiated asthma management protocol on door-to-first-salbutamol-nebulization-time in a pediatric emergency department. *Journal of Emergency Nursing*, 36(5), 428-433. doi: 10.1016/j.jen.2009.11.003

- Rankin, J. A., Then, K. L., & Atack, L. (2013). Can emergency nurses' triage skills be improved by online learning? Results of an experiment. *Journal of Emergency Nursing [JEN]*, 39(1), 20-26. doi: 10.1016/j.jen.2011.07.004
- Retezar, R., Bessman, E., Ding, R., Zeger, S. L., McCarthy, M., L. (2010). The effect of triage diagnostic standing orders on emergency department treatment time. *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, 57(2), 89-99. doi: 10.1016/j.annemergmed.2010.05.016
- Robinson, D. J. (2013). An integrative review: Triage protocols and the effect on ED length of stay. *Journal of Emergency Nursing [JEN]*, 39(4), 398-408. doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2011.12.016
- Salway, R. J., Valenzuela, R., Shoenberger, J. M., Mallon, W. K., Vicellio, A. (2017). Emergency department overcrowding. Evidenced-based answers to frequently asked questions. *Revisita Medica Clinica Las Conde*, 28(2), 213-219. doi: 10.1016/j.rmclc.2017.04.008
- Sayah, A., Rogers, L., Devarajan, K., Kingsley-Rocker, L., & Lobon, L. F. (2014). Minimizing ED wait times and improving patient flow and experience of care. *Emergency Medicine International*, 2014, 1-8. doi: 10.1155/2014/981472
- Seller R. H. & Symons, A. B. (2018). *Differential diagnosis of common complaints*, Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier.
- Sheaff, R., Sherriff, I., & Hennessy, C. H. (2018). Evaluating a dementia learning community: Exploratory study and research implications. *BioMedcial Center Health Services Research*, 18(83), 1-13. DOI 10.1186/s12913-018-2894-3
- Spence, H., & Cappleman, J. (2011). Fostering teamwork in an intermediate care unit. *Nursing Management* 18(3), 20-24, doi: 10.7748/nm2011.06.18.3.20.c8536

- Sprivulis, P. C., Da Silva, J., Jacobs, I. G., Frazer A. R., and Jelinek, G (2006). The association between hospital overcrowding and mortality among patients admitted via Western Australian emergency departments. *The Medical Journal of Australia* 184(5), 208-212. Retrieved from https://www.mja.com.au/system/files/issues/184_05_060306/spr10395_fm.pdf
- Standardized procedure: Treatment and diagnostic protocol [Policy and Procedure]. (2018, March). Retrieved from Project Hospital.
- Stanfield, L. M. (2015). Clinical decision making in triage: An integrative review. *Clinical*, 25(4), 396-403. Doi: 10.1016/j.jen.2015.02.003
- TeAchnology. (2018). *What is Bloom's Taxonomy? How do teachers use it?* Retrieved from <http://www.technology.com/tutorials/teaching/blooms.html>
- The W. Edwards Deming Institute (2018). *PDSA cycle*. Retrieved from <https://deming.org/explore/p-d-s-a>
- Van Donk, P., Tanti, E. R., & Porter, E., J. (2017). Triage and treat model of care: Effective management of minor injuries in the emergency department. *Collegian*, 24(4), 325-330. doi: 10.1016/j.colegn.2016.05.00
- Vezyridis, P. & Timmons, S. (2014). National targets, process transformation and local consequences in an NHS hospital emergency department (ED): Qualitative study. *BioMed Central Emergency Medicine*, 14(12), 1-11. doi: 10.1186/1471-227X-14-12

- Weiss, Steven. (2014). *ED overcrowding and CEDOCS: The community emergency department overcrowding scale* [PowerPoint slides]. Retrieved from the California Hospital Association website: http://www.calhospital.org/sites/main/files/fileattachments/ed_overcrowding_1
- Wolf, L. A., Delao, A. M., Perhats, C., Moon, M. D., & Zavotsky, K. E. (2017). Triageing the emergency department, not the patient: United States emergency nurse's experience of the process. *Journal of Emergency Nursing* [JEN], 44(3), 259-266. doi: 10.1016/j.jen.2017.06.010
- Xu, J. (2016). Toolbox of teaching strategies in nurse education. *Chinese Nursing Research*, 3(2), 54-57. doi: 10.1016/j.cnre.2016.06.002
- Zègre-Hemsey, J., Sommargren, C. E., & Drew, B. J. (2011). Initial ECG acquisition within 10 minutes of arrival at the emergency department in persons with chest pain: Time and gender differences. *Journal of Emergency Nursing* [JEN], 37(1), 109-112. doi:10.1016/j.jen.2009.11.004

APPENDIX A
OUTCOME MEASURES

Emergency Department Metrics	Definition
Daily patient census	The number of patients that are come in to the ED daily.
Door-to-decision	The time a patient enters the ED to the time of disposition decision.
Door-to-admit	The interval when a patient enters the ED to the time they are admitted to a room.
Door-to-discharge	The time a patient enters the ED to the time they leave the ED and discharged home.
Left Without Being Seen (LWBS)	When a patient enters the ED but leaves before they are seen by the ED physician.
Length of Stay (LOS)	The time a patient enters the ED to the time they leave, whether admit or discharge.

(Retezar, Bessman, Ding, Zeger, and McCarthy, 2010)

APPENDIX B

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Triage

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
1-Evaluation of reliability between ESI category designated by EMS personnel and ED triage RN	Prospective, Observational study Evaluation reliability ESI scores assigned by fire department EMS & triage RNs	Sept - Nov 2008; Academic center with ED residency program 606-bed tertiary care hospital	EMS providers assigned T category when pt arrived ED Pearson χ^2 Test used to evaluation for differences in prehospital provider accuracy	45 cases were perfect agreement between EMS & T nurse ESI Level 1 A=94.7%, S=0% SP=97.3%	1) Not reliable - Moderate concordance between EMS & RN ESI triage assignments. 2) Medic ESI acuity assignment poor → after training in RN-oriented program EMS not able to effectively use this T tool in prehospital setting to assign patient acuity
2-Evaluate validity of EMS Triage category using ESI instrument. (Buschhorn, Strout, Sholl, & Baumann, 2013).	ER nurses at institution receive formal ESI training before being assigned to T including the completion of a self-study module, a written test, and 24 hours of precepted time at T with experience T RN Paramedics receive same training; <i>Sensitivity</i> represented the ability of EMS to correctly assign pts to appropriate ESI designation;	Participants- 60 fire department paramedics & EMT 43 ED T RNs Sample patients were those that were brought in by EMS Medics and EMT-trained to use the ESI Training sessions were conducted in exactly same manner Medics assign T level at the end of transport	Assessed validity of ESI instrument when applied by EMS in prehospital setting by evaluation. S & SP for each ESI level RN assigned ESI scores as the gold standard for each case EMS provider triage assignments -2 categories:	ESI Level 2 A=69.3% S=57.1% SP=84.9% ESI level 3 A=68.0% S=67.9% Sp=68.1% ESI level 4 A=90.1% S=33.3% Sp=93.1% ESI level 5=0 experience-not found to be statistically significant	Limitations: only 3 were recorded by nursing to be ESI level 4, and there were no patients triaged by nursing as ESI level 5. limited ability of study to eval EMS providers ability to triage in lower acuity

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
	<p><i>Specificity</i> represented their ability to correctly NOT assign pts to a particular ESI level;</p> <p>Approved IRB</p>	<p>75 pts transports were included</p> <p>26 EMS < 10 years of experience & 49 >10+ years of experience</p>	<p>“triaged correctly” & “triaged incorrectly”;</p> <p>Triage RN ESI designation assigned was gold-standard</p>		<p>EMS not familiar w resource allocation & utilization in ED</p> <p>RN T acuity may not have been completely accurate.</p>

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
The purpose is to develop a role description of the triage nurse (Ebrahimi, Mirhaghi, Mazlom, Heydari, Nassehi, & Jafari, 2016)	Modified Delphi study Approved by Research Ethics Committee	March to Oct 2014 3 Rounds of study Mashhad University of Medical Sciences.	Round 1-Lit Review-Data collected from different databases- data collected was on attributes of a triage nurse. Exclusion- study not approved by their emergency association or college	Round 1- 23 studies chosen from 353 articles, 7 included for Final analysis 62 items extracted from final studies Round 2- 31% response rate 80% of expert must like the items/ characteristics of T nurse 43 items remained at end	Results conflicted with other studies in that T nurse ordering x-rays did NOT expedite the pt flow. Expanding the role of T nurse brought more satisfaction Fast tracking pts and prioritizing care produced positive outcomes
	Rounds: 1-Extensive ROL “What are the attributes of triage nurse?” 2-Questionnaire sent to 38 experts about initial tasks & role of T nurse 3-Modified questionnaire sent to expert panel Questionnaire items were r/t basics, ethics, triage assessment, decision making, informing, competencies, environment, and documentation	Confidentiality & Anonymity was secured Round 1- Feb Round 2-May convened 38 purposeful sample of content expert of ER medicine experts and emergency nursing scholars. Round 3= July 6 Female Average age 38	Data collected until saturation Round 2- Researchers had to consent on articles used by rating the liking of the article on a Likert-type scale Proportions & % calculated for ordinal data of Likert -type response scale Analyzed with MS Excel 2007	Round 3-58% response rate, 43 items remained at the end. Items were excluded if it did not reach an 80% consensus	Consensus that T nurse is accountable for safe triage practices NP optimizes QI measures and finances Limitations: modified Delphi method was used. Standard definitions for modified not available

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Study aimed to see if ED crowding affected pt T destination, acuity & readmission to ED (O'Connor, Gatién, Weir, & Calder, 2014)	Retrospective pilot study ICD 10 codes used to identify pts with chest pain & shortness of breath Ottawa Hospital Research Ethics Board approved study 500 eligible pt visits >18yrs old Canadian Triage Acuity System (CTAS) -5 category triage system	Large urban tertiary care Canadian academic teaching hospital 2 ED hospitals Jan1- Dec 31, 2010 Internet-based random number generator	Variables recorded: triage time and date, triage score, triage destination, time of initial physician assessment, investigations ordered, and referrals made.	CP & SOB pts were assigned a CTAS score of 2 were triaged to the nonmonitored area of the ED significantly more often when the ED was crowded (25.0% vs. 16.3%, P = 0.02) Did not find that ED crowding conditions resulted in an increase in return visits to the ED within 14 days Increase in time to physician initial assessment for patients triaged during crowding conditions.	ED crowding influences triage destination → Longer wait times for high acuity pts Did not lead to increase of discharged patients to the ED Limitations: Restricted to a single institution that encompasses two large tertiary care EDs and we were only able to detect return visits to our institution and not to other institutions in our area Study was under-powered Retrospective study- unable to determine if CTAS scores were appropriately assigned for the patients in the study

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
<p>Purpose of study- explore ED nurses' understanding of triage process, & identify facilitators and barriers to assigning accurate acuity level</p> <p>(Wolf, Delao, Perhats, Moon & Zavotsky, 2017).</p>	<p>Exploratory qualitative study;</p> <p>Focus-group Interviews;</p> <p>Focus-group sessions & transcriptions done;</p> <p>Field notes were analyzed using open coding, simultaneous coding, and sub-coding techniques</p>	<p>ED nurses (N = 26), Semi-structured focus group discussion;</p> <p>Participants were at a nursing conference</p>	<p>Descriptive statistics were performed;</p> <p>Data analysis done by team members;</p> <p>IBM SPSS Statistics 22 database-demographics; Analysis & thematic comparison, & member checking & peer debriefings - all undertaken to determine saturation & enhance the credibility and dependability of the study's findings</p>	<p>5 themes identified:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) "Sick or not sick," 2) "Competency/qualifications," 3) "Triageing the emergency department, not the patient," 4) "The unexpected," 5) "Barriers and facilitators." 	<p>Use of triage levels to determine acuity & appropriate resources for pt varies in accuracy between ED nurses;</p> <p>Distress at the environmental conditions (staffing, & limited time), personal conditions (burnout/ compassion fatigue) interferes w high-quality & safe pt care;</p> <p>Pt triage can be different due to time, experience, & expertise.</p> <p>Limitation: small self-selected group; findings may not be generalizable</p>

Note. A: Accuracy; CTAS- Canadian Triage Acuity System; ED: emergency department; ESI: Emergency Severity Index; EMS: Emergency Medical Services (paramedics); IRB: Institutional Review Board; NP: nurse practitioner; pt: patient; QI: quality improvement; S: sensitivity; Sp: specificity; T: triage

Table 2

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Interventions

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Examine effects of initiating diagnostic tests in waiting room on total time in ED & LWBS rates (Begaz, Elashoff, Grogan, Talan, & Taira, 2016).	Prospective randomized controlled trial; Stable patients were randomized to either RME WRDT or RME-only groups RME WRDT group had lab & imaging studies ordered; Primary- time in an ED bed; Secondary- total ED time & rate of LWBS	Public hospital ED Pts in waiting room waiting MD evaluation 1,659 patients; July 2014 - May 2015; RME WRDT Group- 848 pts RME-only Group-811 pts	Linear and logistic regression models were used to compare outcomes between group	Pts in RME WRDT (245") group had significantly shorter M time in ED bed than RME (277") -only group RME (504")-only group: Had significantly longer M LOS than RME WRDT (460") group. 78 of 848 pts LWBS in the RME WRDT group compared with 103 of 811 RME-only group	Initiating diagnostic testing in WR = ↓ time spent in ED bed, ↓total LOS, & ↓LWBS rates; Initiating diagnostic testing improves ED throughput; At end of their ED visit, pts in RME WRDT group had significantly more types of diagnostic tests than pts in RME-only

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
<p>Tested a protocol to automatically order CXR in triage for pts with signs and symptoms of PNA to ↓ time to antibiotics</p> <p>(Cooper, Datner, & Pines, 2008).</p>	<p>Retrospective study of pts admitted with PNA;</p> <p>Tested the protocol on time to antibiotics;</p> <p>EMTRAC - computer tracking & charting system;</p> <p>2-phase study- 1- identify pt-level factors (demographics; s/s) 2- prospective before-after study testing impact of protocol on time to antibiotics & time to CXR for admitted pts with PNA</p>	<p>University of Pennsylvania Hospital (Philadelphia, PA), urban, tertiary care, academic medical center with ED census 57,000 visits;</p> <p>Protocol included pts w cc of CP, SOB, URI, hemoptysis, fever, & cough;</p> <p>pts >50 yrs + with abnormal VS & pts <50yrs old w comorbidity of immunocompromise, cancer, DM transplant, or chronic alcoholism - had a CXR ordered automatically</p>	<p>Used standard descriptive statistics with 95% CIs and t-tests, χ^2 tests, and Mann-Whitney U tests to compare difference between control period & intervention period;</p> <p>All data analysis performed using Stata 9.0</p>	<p>Protocol was only 35% sensitive in identifying admitted pts with PNA;</p> <p>Time to CXR decision rule positive in 165 of 177 admit pts with PNA & 93% sensitive;</p> <p>Time to antibiotics ↓ from 4.2 hours during control period to 3.4 hours;</p> <p>Triage CXR ↓ from 3 hours to 2 hours;</p> <p>Pt diagnosed PNA time from triage to antibiotics was 3 hours compared to 4.1 hours</p>	<p>Automated CXR to triage reduces time to antibiotics in admitted pts with PNA;</p> <p>CXR ordered at triage for pts suspected for PNA ↓ time CXR & time to antibiotics</p> <p>Limitations: Protocol may have resulted in delay in radiographs for other pts;</p> <p>Did not control for ED overcrowding</p>

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Evaluate ED radiology exams & interpreted prior to a documented clinical assessment. (Hanna, Rohatgi, Shekhani, & Johnson, 2016).	Pt times were documented: ED arrival, departure, LOS, imaging order time, image availability, radiology report, triage note, ED MD note, & lab results; TAT calculated: ED arrival to time rad. order, time of order to time of completion, & time completion to final radiology report	600 retrospectives consecutive ED cases received either a CT, XR or US; Data acquired from 3 university hospitals Level-2 trauma centers – ED; info acquired from databank	Using EMR, cross-referenced each pt & extracted full triage & ED reports into Database Descriptive & demographic info collected; Examined cases where imaging exam completed before triage note, & cases where radiology report was available before triage note	No difference in any groups, implying the TAT for radiologists was not affected by the clinical or lab info available at the time of interpretation; 33% of ED pts had incomplete clinical info available for radiologist at the time of interpretation; 10% of ED imaging exams were ordered & completed before ED provider clinical notes were started	Clinical information improves diagnostic accuracy; 20.5% of radiographs, 6.5% of CTs, and 6% of US were interpreted prior to the ED MD report & clinical narrative; 57.5% of XR cases interpreted with missing clinical or lab information = 23.5% US & 18.5% CT Lacked clinical info did not affect radiology interpretation of TAT but did impact exam selection & diagnostic accuracy Limitations: Retrospective study & conducted at a single site entity; data collection timeframe was short

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes	
The study aims to examine the relationship between triage and treat model of care and pt outcomes: effectiveness, LOS, pt flow & pt satisfaction. (Van Donk, Tanti, & Porter, 2017)	Descriptive cross-sectional study	Convenience sample	Data collection via phone 1 month from ED visit	LOS in for triage & tx = 80 min. Mean LOS= 19 min	Clinical significance: T & treatment is a safe & effective option of care for minor injury presentations and minor wound care management	
	IV: Triage & Treat model (treat pt after triaging them)	Regional Victoria ED, Australia	Interview questions: 1) Clinical r/t problem & treatment 2) Pt satisfaction (Likert scale) 3) Open-ended question & education for ongoing care & follow-up	Triage & treat model of care demonstrated ↓ wait times & tx times, ↓ LOS, ↑ pt satisfaction without significant complications		
	DV: WT, pt satisfy, LOS	March 2012- 2013	117 participants 42 F, 72 M mean age= 27 (13 months -67 years old)	Data Analysis: Demographics, Descriptive statistical analysis (responses to open-ended questions)	Mean LOS = 19 min SD= 14.3 Wound management most common treatment 83% (n=97) Pt requested f/u afterwards: 23% (n=27) → 67% (n=17) was planned f/u 37% (n=10) had unplanned f/u	Negative outcome: Some stated they received poor wound care; Can be contributed to different triage nurses' practices
	Australasian Triage Scale (ATS)	Majority 38% participants: 0-10 years old range (38%)	Inclusions: pt T as Cat 4 & 5, informed consent & fit in criteria: Wound management, Plaster of Paris check, minor burns, suspected distal limb fracture	Interview questions reviewed by Monash University researchers	Positive themes: 1) timely treatment 2) effective model of care Negative themes: RN poor wound education & care	Limitations: Difficult recruiting & retaining senior RN for triage (lack of interest)
	Cat 1-3 acute care Cat 4-5 fast track		Exclusions: intoxicated ETOH/ drugs, injuries with LOC, mental health, pts not appropriate for T & treatment			Small # participants in non-wound category → unable to make conclusion
	Pts T as Cat 4 & 5 were seen in T & tx accordingly, expediting ED visit					Single ED setting → larger setting would provide wider mix of pt population, more RN avail Note: Different approach to triage RN ↑ autonomy; concern is level of skills among RNs
	Senior RN able to T, tx and dc pts w minor complaints					
Pt care & tx regime by use of flow chart						
Approved by Hospital Research Ethics Committee						

Note. CP: chest pain; CT: assmt: assessment; computed tomography; CXR: chest xray; DM: Diabetes Mellitus; EMTRAC: University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, Hospital computer tracking and charting system; f/u: follow up; LOC: level of conscious; LOS: length of stay; rad: radiology; PNA: Pneumonia; RME: rapid medical evaluation; RME WRDT group that had lab & imaging studies ordered; RME-only group: group that did not have any lab & imaging studies ordered; s/s: signs and symptoms; SD: standard deviation; SOB: short of breath; TAT: turn-around-times; WRDT: waiting room diagnostic testing; XR: xray; URI: upper respiratory infection; US: Ultrasound; VS: vital signs.

Table 3

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Overcrowding

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Objective of study was to determine time pts wait until they are triaged (Houston, Sanchez, Fischer, Volz, Wolfe, 2015)	Observational study Observer 24/ Not human subject research, no IRB Problem: Inaccurate & underestimated wait time and unrecorded times cause significant error in calculation of timed metrics Trial period was done 2 weeks prior to data collection	Convenience sample Urban, academic, tertiary care center ED Nov 1, 2012 to Oct 1, 2013 All pts enrolled in study within dates	Walk-in pt arrivals to ED goes to triage booth; When EMS arrivals to ED, pt goes to an ED bed: therefore, Triage time is the same as arrival time If T booth occupied, an observer records the time of arrival “pre-triage” Difference was calculated from the time of arrival and triage.	50,576 pts total 7.795 pt waited T Longest wait between 10am – 8pm high census time Median time arrival to T was 11 min 4,286 pt (8%) waited >10min for T 55% of those who waited, waited additional 10+minutes With additional pts coming in the longer the wait times for T	Data showed that door-to-doctor times are longer with the current standards of reporting Significant amount of pts waiting >10min, which is 30% of national door-to-doctor time Limitations: Conducted at single institution Study looked only at time waiting for triage Future studies can evaluate if ↑ wait has ↑ adverse effect or bad outcomes

Note. ETOH- alcohol, T- triage, Tx- treat

Table 4

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Standardized Protocol in Triage

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
To develop a patient-focus approach to improve the quality of care in the unit;	Case study action research method; Steps: 1) Establish framework (fw) 2) Applying fw to case study	Maltese Hospital Accident & Emergency Unit (A&E); Acute care	Many factors addressed: (experience of doctors, availability of hospital beds, triage, wait times, faster pt flow)	Pt TAT ↓ 2 hours Triage changed from 3 tier system to ESI 5-Level, more valid and scientific in approach;	Adoption of fw allowed structured process of identifying problematic issues but also provides plans & improvement & implementation;
Manage patients effectively & ↓ unnecessary admissions	Use of conceptual fw to improve quality pt care 1) Quality management fw- Quality Function Deployment (QFD): identify areas that needs improvements 2) Logical framework approach (LFA): helps develop plans for improvement; 3) Validating proposed QI fw for adoption to unit;	850 bed hospital in Malta; 112 surveys sent to patients	were laid out to be weighted on which is more important of address; Formula created to see how much importance for different categories; Once identified, teams targeted to solve problems: pt flow, accurate triage, experience T nurse, stand protocol, shorter administration times were some issues addressed	Guidelines and protocols for medical emergencies increased from 1 to 12 protocols – adult & pediatric guidelines based on early warning signs, chest pain, asthma, pulmonary emboli, head injury etc; ↓ wait times to see ED MD; Customer complaints ↓ 513 to 208 in 1 year	Study easy to adopt Limitation: Did not address wait times in lobby No research articles were found on QFD application; Note- article good for the initiation of ED SP
(Buttigieg, Dey, & Cassar, 2016)	Application of fw: 6 Steps				

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Determine the effect of REACT in ER metrics (Chan, Killeen, Kelly, & Guss, 2005).	Before & after intervention design	Urban, academic; 37,000 census/year	Outcome measures: Wait times, LWBS, LOS, census, admission;	↓ LWBS 42% ↓ LOS 31 min ↓ DC pts 35 min ↓ admit times 11 min ↓ wait times 22.7%	Significant decrease LWBS, wait time, LOS from pre-REACT vs. post.;
	6 months pre-post data from intervention;	Real time patients during intervention times	Data received from EMR;	8% pt had testing done in triage	Limitations: Not generalizable, hospital was teaching academic, had residents & attendings;
	Changes to ED process: Eliminated full registration;	If no open beds, T RN calls MD for lab/diagnostic orders;			
	Extra ECT during busiest hours				LOS, LWBS times higher than national average Only did 6-month implementation, 1 year or greater might yield better results

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Does RN initiated standard protocol improved timeliness of care (Douma, Drake, O'Dochartaigh, & Smith, 2016)	Quality Improvement; Updated SP; 30 nurses given 1 hour training; 3 groups separated by years exp. IV: Pts who met inclusion criteria for diagnosis, separated into their groups DV: SP pts Statistical analysis --blinded fashion.; Ethics Community Consensus Initiative's Ethics Screening Tool	The Royal Alexandra Hospital ED Canada 55 bed LWBS rate: 10% 42 days enrollment; 143 patients: 76 protocol & 67 control group.	Primary outcome: 1) time to dx tests 2) time to treatment 3) time to consultation 4) LOS Secondary outcome: RN satisfaction	Protocols: ↓ time to acetaminophen for pain/fever DV- 54 min IV- 240 min; CP protocol: DV- 35 min IV 114 min ↓ time to troponin by 79 min. ; Fracture hip protocol: Go to Xray- DV: 42 min IV: 299 min ↓ LOS 224 min Vaginal bleed with pregnancy: ↓ 232 min DV- 295 min IV- 527 min; Lower Abdominal pain: 181 min difference	Specific written protocols for groups improve time to tests, meds, ↓ LOS & expedited admissions; Rn ↑ satisfaction 87% believe tests benefit pts; 97% confident MD would order those diagnostic tests; Limitations: several days of bed closures & understaffing may have affected the results; Monitoring for adherence is challenging

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Evaluate effects of diagnostic standing orders in T with 1) treatment times 2) boarding times (Retezar, Bessman, Ding, Zeger, & McCarthy, 2010)	Retrospective cohort study Jan 2007-Aug 2009 Compared pts who received: 1) Full (F) SP orders 2) Partial (P) SP orders	Academic ED Level II Trauma 57,000 pt census per year 33 acute & 8 non-acute beds 15,188 total pts 1) Full SP=25% 2) Partial SP=56% 3) Trad. room orders=19% Inclusion: Pt w CP, abdominal pain, SOB, GU and waited 15 min for bed Exclusion: LWBS, ESI 1, 4&5, waited < 15 min for bed, missing times	Meditech Client Server - data extraction: 1) demographic 2) clinical characteristics (cc, ESI, mode arrival, T RN) 3) date, time T, time to room, time to admit, time to disposition, disposition status, date and time orders placed Outcome measures: ED treatment time (decision), discharge time, admit time, boarding time Propensity score done to balance measured characteristics between all groups by using the Multivariate Linear regression model	Mean treatment times: ↓ 52 min after SP (17%) → Not significant Boarding time ↓ 12% → Not significant SOB treatment times ↓ 14% → Not significant	First study for SP and treatment times F/P SP ↓ 16% ED treatment P ↓ 17% F vs P, results inconsistent time → Not significant More study needed to see which tests most appropriate in T Significant ↓ treatment wait times with different diagnosis No effects on boarding time Limitations: Did not study other treatments initiated after pt in room. Downside SP can bias provider decision making if not taking PMH in consideration

Note. 2*: secondary; cc: chief complaint; DC: discharge; DV: dependent variable; ECT: emergency care technician; EMR: Electronic medical record; ESI: emergency severity index; F: full SP orders; fw: framework; GU: genital-urinary; IV: independent variable; LOS- Length of Stay; LWBS- Left without being seen; P: partial SP orders QFD: Quality Function Deployment; PMH: past medical history; SP: Standard Protocols; T= triage; TAT: Turn-around time; tx: treatment

Table 5

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Electric Learning Module

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Study assessed med. student's medical knowledge & impact of e-modules infection control & congenital infections (Khasawneh, Simonsen, Snowden, Higgins, & Beck, 2016).	Descriptive study; 3 formats e-Module was developed: 1- text monograph, 2- PPT 3- narrated PPT lecture; 67 participants 63% of them visited at least 1 e-module, a 15-item pre- & post-test, & self-assessment survey	Single-university study Conducted on 3 rd year med. students in pediatric rotation; Academic year 2013-2014	Wilcox used to rank sum test for dependent samples; Comparisons of pre & post-surveys were calculated in aggregate as well as categorized	Students' confidence with <i>infection control</i> was not improved after completing the modules: (91% pretest vs. 76% posttest); Confidence increased with <i>congenital Infections</i> : (37% pretest vs. 69% posttest). e-Modules did not improve student performance on NBME or post-test; perceived as satisfactory and to have improved confidence	e-Modules for infection control & congenital infections were satisfactory to students & only improved self-confidence; No improvement in knowledge in either pre- & posttest scores or NBME results; Only 1/3 of the students found traditional text-based monograph helpful for either topic

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion Limitations, Notes
Determine impact of 3 changes to the standard online learning on accuracy of triage skills of ED nurses (Rankin, Then, & Attack, 2013).	Experimental study;	Centennial College, Toronto, Ontario, Canada;	Descriptive statistic;	Triage accuracy:	Online learning does impact clinical practice;
	2 groups- All received same content & learning activity.	6 hospitals across Canada participated with chart audits.	t-test used to compare & summarize total scores post-intervention grp.	C grp- 69.8%; E grp- 72.1%	Triage accuracy for all nurses 70% (improvement);
	Intervention group (E)= 65, extra tutorial, online discussion, & work project;	367 charts audited	Kruskal-Wallis test- compared scores tween OLSI groups.	Workplace project (E grp) significant impact on clinical & triage practices;	E-learning provide effective education experience, improved triage accuracy;
	Control group (C)= 67; LDS- questions admin before tests;	N=203 nurses participated in study, ER nurse expert reviewer with triage system;	Face and content validity established;	No significant differences between OLSI scores of 2 groups;	Facilitated transfer of knowledge from individuals to other staff/ administrators;
	OLSI- measures RN's experience after tests	CTAS did chart audits; compared CTAS code to the code assigned on pts' chart.		78% knowledge improved; 76% said pt simulations helpful; 53% said not enough time to learn CTAS at work; 75% said they liked the Web course training	Limitations: No statistically significant difference in accuracy between both groups, nurses & expert. Possible need larger sample size

Note: CTAS: Canadian Triage and Acuity Scale; grp: group; LDS- Learner Demographic Survey; NBME: National Board of Medical Examiners; OLSI: Online Learner Support Instrument; PPT: PowerPoint;

Table 6

Table of Evidence for Emergency Department Throughput: Literature Review

Purpose	Study Design, Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements	Results	Conclusion, Limitations & Notes
Emergency Severity Index (ESI)	ENA & ACEP recommend ESI 5 level T system	Literature review 2002-2014	126 studies resulted 11 were included	Themes: 1) clinical information 2) education & experience 3) characteristic, attitudes of T nurses 4) working environment	In order to T pts, the T nurse must use clinical decision-making skills, integration of clinical info while relying on their education.& experience, along with their environment without using their biases
The purpose literature review- determine current research to better understand clinical decision-making skills	Levels: 1) Immediate (life-saving intervention) 2) Emergent (pt should not wait for tx)		Articles organized in matrix method 8 topics used: Caring Nursing Patient Interactions scale (CNPI-23) - measured RN attitudes	Vital signs, pain score, med history & allergies -most import → use it along with clinical judgement	Exclusions: study not related to decision making process;
Purpose- determine what clinical decision-making skills are necessary for triage	3) Urgent (pt stable to wait - >2 R) 4) Less urgent (1R) 5) Non-urgent (0 R)			Triage RN min 1 year experience Attitude & characteristics: good communication, work at fast pace, flexible in role Environment- foster team work → good communicative, leadership, autonomy → accuracy of triage	Implications for practice- train T nurses on specific triage educational practices and ESI levels
(Stanfield, 2015)					

Note. ACEP: American College of Emergency Physicians; Charac: character

APPENDIX C

STANDARDIZED PROTOCOL FOR EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

 DEPARTMENTAL POLICIES AND PROCEDURES	Page(s):	1 of 8	
	Section:	ED1095	
	Saved As:	Standardized Procedure: Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	
	Formulated:	2/09	
Subject:	Standardized Procedure: Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	Reviewed:	03/10,06/11,09/13,09/14,11/15
Manual:	Emergency Department	Revised:	7/12, 11/17
Governing Board Approval		Date:	3/18

POLICY

Approved registered nurses in the Emergency Department may initiate emergency treatment as defined in this policy if a physician is not immediately available.

EDUCATION, TRAINING AND EXPERIENCE

Advanced Cardiac Life Support Provider Status
Initial Evaluation - satisfactory probationary period by Clinical Director or designee
Ongoing Evaluation - annual performance appraisal

SUPERVISION

The procedure will be under the general supervision of the Emergency Department Medical Director. The physical presence of the Medical Director or any physician in the facility is not required.

CRITERIA

Emergency room or other physician is not immediately available.
Upon assessment, a patient in the Emergency Room exhibits signs and symptoms, which require emergent treatment.
PEDS patients are 14 years old or younger.

DOCUMENTATION

Clinical assessment and treatment and response will be entered in the patient's Emergency Room Record

QUALIFIED PERSONNEL

Names of qualified Registered Nurses on file in the office the ICU/ ER Director / HR Office

PROCEDURE

Qualified Emergency Room registered nurses may initiate the following treatment for the specific conditions. Obtain Vital Signs initially and PRN according to interventions or clinical needs. Notify the Emergency Room physician as soon as possible:

ANAPHYLAXIS WITH HYPOTENSION / UNSTABLE AIRWAY**MD evaluation immediately**

Cardiac monitoring, continuous
Continuous O2 saturation monitoring
Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
250 mL IV bolus times one of isotonic solution (0.9% saline) for adults, and 20cc kg IV bolus times one for pediatrics. This should be followed by isotonic solution rate 50cc hour for adults and 15cc hour for pediatrics. MD reevaluation within one hour.

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RT evaluation: Airway/ Trach kit at bedside

Requires ED MD order:

ADULT: Give Benadryl 25 mg IV. Have available at bedside: Epinephrine 1:1000, 0.3 mg IM

PEDS: Give Benadryl 1 mg/kg IV. Have available at bedside: Epinephrine 1:1000, 0.01mg/kg subcutaneous (max dose 0.3 mg). See - Addendum A for Pediatric dosing chart.

See Symptomatic Hypotension below

SYMPTOMATIC HYPOTENSION**MD Evaluation Immediately**

Lie patient down. Trendelenberg or leg elevation PRN
Cardiac monitoring, continuous
Continuous O2 saturation monitoring
Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
If anaphylaxis with hypotension also follow regimen above

ADULT IV fluid challenge:

Except in patients with signs and symptoms of CHF, fluid bolus 250mL normal saline for symptomatic SBP < 100 with HR > 110 when hypovolemia/dehydration suspected as underlying cause, notify ED MD.

PEDS IV fluid challenge:

NS or RL 20 mL/Kg IV fluid challenge. May repeat twice PRN to maintain systolic BP from {70 + (2 x Kg)} up to 100mmHg, notify ED MD.

New Onset Weak and Dizzy

- Obtain Fingertick blood glucose
- 12 - Lead ECG

CHEST PAIN**MD evaluation immediately**

- 12 - Lead ECG within 3 minutes handed to MD
- O2 per mask or nasal cannula at 2 - 4 L/minute
- If chest pain persist after implementation of above notify ED MD.
- ASA 324 mg P.O. (ASA 300 mg rectally if unable to take po or NPO) if no contraindications, i.e.: bleeding tendencies or ASA allergy or on coumadin
- Cardiac monitoring, continuous
- Continuous O2 saturation monitoring
- Vital Signs initially and PRN according to interventions or clinical needs
- Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)

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- IV isotonic solution at TKO rate (0.9% saline at 20 mL/hour)
- Labs: CBC, BMP, Magnesium, Troponin , LDL
- Portable Chest X-ray
- ACLS protocol PRN
- If any medications are given via protocol, the administering nurse will write an order for the medication "per protocol"

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE INFANTS/CHILDREN

Temperature greater than 100.4
 Acetaminophen 15 mg/Kg suppository Per Rectum or suspension PO (if none given within 4 hours)
 AND/OR Ibuprofen 10 mg/Kg suspension PO (if none given within 6 hours)
 If core temperature 104° or greater: Notify ED MD and ADD appropriate cooling measures

Notify ED MD:

- Any symptomatic febrile patient
- All infants 0 – 90 days with documented core temperature > 100.3
- History of Sickle Cell disease, Immunocompromise, chronic disease (Diabetes)
- Febrile seizure, Petechiae, listlessness, poor eye contact, complicated birth history

WHEEZING WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

MD evaluation immediately

Pulse oximetry
 Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
 Bag-valve-mask and high flow O₂ ventilatory assist PRN

ALL MEDICATIONS REQUIRE A MD ORDER:

Proventil (Albuterol) 2.5 mg unit dose and Atrovent 0.5 mg unit dose by aerosol (nebulizer treatment)
 Call Respiratory Therapist to assist PRN

ADULT:

If no contraindications to steroids, Decadron (Dexamethasone) 10mg IV push (IM if unable to give IV)

PEDS:

If no contraindications to steroids, Decadron 0.6mg/kg IV push up to 10 mg. (IM if unable to give IV)

RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

MD evaluation immediately.

Cardiac monitoring, continuous
 Pulse oximetry
 ABG
 Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%) Bag-valve-mask and high flow
 O₂ ventilatory assist PRN
 12 - Lead ECG
 Portable Chest X-ray

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SEIZURES (not including febrile seizures)

MD evaluation immediately

Seizure precautions: bed rails up and padded
 Pulse oximetry
 Core temperature
 Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
 STAT blood glucose via Accucheck meter
 IV isotonic solution at TKO rate (0.9% saline at 20 mL/hour for adults; 15 mL/hour for pediatrics)

Requires ED MD order:

ADULT - Lorazepam (Ativan) 2mg IV push (IM if unable to give IV). Repeat in 10 to 15 minutes if seizure activity is not abated

PEDS - Lorazepam 0.1mg/Kg IV push (IM if unable to give IV). If seizure activity is not abated within 10 minutes give Lorazepam 0.05mg/Kg IV push (IM if unable to give IV). Do not exceed 0.4 mg/Kg total dosage.

OVERDOSE

MD evaluation immediately

Cardiac monitoring, continuous; Pulse oximetry
 STAT blood glucose via Accucheck meter
 Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
 Contact Poison Control: (800) 411-8080
 IV isotonic solution at TKO rate (0.9% saline at 20 mL/hour for adults; 15 mL/hour for pediatrics)
 Do not initiate any type of N-G or oral-gastric tube without MD order:

Restraints per Restraint policy
 Suicide Precautions
 Urine specimen for toxicology screen

Requires ED MD order:

Charcoal P.O. only if patient tolerates Fowler's position and has intact gag reflex.

ADULTS - Charcoal 1Gm/Kg.P.O. Give 50% of dose as charcoal with sorbitol and 50% as plain charcoal. Mix with water, soda or juice PRN for palatability

PEDS - Plain charcoal 1Gm/Kg. Mix with water or soda or juice PRN for palatability.
 Narcan 0.4mg IV push if decreased level of consciousness

PROCEDURE:

Qualified Emergency Room registered nurses may initiate the following diagnostic tests for the specific conditions. These protocols are for diagnostic tests only and do not describe any treatments, interventions or medication. They take the following factors into consideration:

- Chief complaint

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- Mechanism of injury
- Clinical picture
- Female patient's ability to menstruate (i.e.: ability to get pregnant)

The RN applies the nursing process to the above factors in order to determine which, if any, protocol driven tests should be ordered by the nurse.

Pain assessment and notify ED MD for pain medication as needed prior to diagnostic study as appropriate

Order sets may be initiated at Triage, ED MD evaluation immediately

Before ordering any radiographic test on a female who menstruates do a urine pregnancy test. Only order test if pregnancy test is negative.
Can have patient sign wavier for extremity and apply shield.

Do not send any neck pain patients to waiting room without ED MD evaluation. (They must meet same criteria as patients "cleared" from back boards.

- No midline neck tenderness
- No altered mental status or signs of intoxication
- No other severely painful injuries that could distract the patient from their neck pain
- No numbness or weakness

FRACTURES and SPRAINS:

Immobilize affected extremity, elevation, and ice
X-Ray of affected extremity (including joint above and below injury if traumatic)
Tylenol or Motrin for pain, pediatrics and adults (Log Bone Fracture)

HEAD INJURY (Traumatic):

MD evaluation immediately

(* RN's should not be ordering CT's)

- IF ANY loss of consciousness occurred after the injury
- Altered mental status
- Vomiting 3 or more times since the head injury
- Severe headache

VAGINAL BLEEDING:

Urine pregnancy test (i.e.: urine HCG, a.k.a. UCG)
If UCG is negative order CBC
If UCG is positive order CBC, Type and Rh, Quantitative beta HCG (if < 12 weeks gestation), Pelvic US

EPIGASTRIC OR UPPER ABDOMINAL PAIN:

CBC, CMP, Lipase, UA
12 – Lead ECG (if > 40 years of age)

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LOWER ABDOMINAL PAIN:

CBC, BMP, UA, UCG (for females who can menstruate)

WEAK/DIZZY (NOT VERTIGO) AND > 60 YEARS OF AGE:

MD evaluation immediately

CBC, BMP, D-Dimer, Troponin, UA, PCXR, 12 – Lead ECG

GI BLEEDING:

MD evaluation immediately

Scant rectal bleeding or spotting: CBC

Significant rectal bleeding or melena or hematemesis: CBC, BMP, PT

UTI:

UA (notify ED MD if unable to void after 20 minutes)

Vomiting and Diarrhea under 3 years of age

- Obtain stool if possible (send on MD request)
- Trial of oral fluids, give 2 ounces every 10 minutes

LACERATIONS WITH POSSIBILITY OF FOREIGN BODIES:

X-Ray soft tissue of affected area

**EPINEPHRINE PEDIATRIC DOSING CHART
FOR ANAPHYLAXIS WITH HYPOTENSION/UNSTABLE AIRWAY**

EPINEPHRINE INJECTION
1:1000 AMPULE

CONCENTRATION: 1 MG/ML
MAXIMUM DOSE: 0.3 MG

Wt (kg)	Wt (lbs)	Dose (ml)
5	11	0.05
10	22	0.1
15	33	0.15
20	44	0.2
25	55	0.25
30	66	0.3
> 30	66	0.3

Lacerations in Peds <14 years

Apply EMLA or LET to affected area

Tylenol or Motrin for Pain ask MD for Dosage

APPENDIX D

PROJECT HOSPITAL CONSENT LETTER

California State University, Los Angeles
Institutional Review Board

May 15, 2018

To Whom It May Concern:

Thoa (Katrina) Wallace MSN, RN is an employee of ours, and she has our permission to conduct a Quality Improvement Project entitled, Emergency Department Throughput: Initiating a Standardized Protocol for Triage. She will be teaching the nursing staff and will be initiating a new standard protocol in triage. She will also be conducting a retrospective chart review pre-implementation and post implementation of the standard protocol. The goal is to improve our ED metrics and throughput by initiating patient care in triage. The ED standard protocol is a strict, guided order-set that was developed by our ED physicians and has been approved by our Governing Board.

Katrina will be looking at several ED metrics: Door-to-decision, Door-to-Admission, Door-to-Discharge, Length of Stay and Left Without Being Seen rates. All information will be retrieved from our electronic medical record system. She will be looking at patients 18 years and older, who were seen in the ED between August 2017 to December 2017 (pre-intervention) as well as August 2018 to December 2018 (post-intervention). There will be no direct patient contact, all information will be de-identified, and our hospital does not have a IRB that we need to go through. Once this information is gathered and outcomes identified, it will be shared with the involved stakeholders and would help our institution to address the problem of ED overcrowding.

We understand that by doing this innovative project, Katrina is also fulfilling her studies in the Doctoral of Nursing Practice program at the California State University Consortium and California State University, Los Angeles. We approve this project and look forward to her results. If you have any questions or concerns, please feel free to contact me.

Sincerely,

A rectangular area where the signature of the Chief Nursing Officer has been redacted with a blue-grey pattern.

Chief Nursing Officer

APPENDIX E

IRB APPROVAL: CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES

Office Memorandum

DATE:	June 26, 2018
TO:	Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC
FROM:	California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB
PROJECT TITLE:	[1254949-1] Improving Emergency Department Throughput: Initiation of a New Standard Protocol 17-219
REFERENCE #:	
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	APPROVED
APPROVAL DATE:	June 26, 2018
EXPIRATION DATE:	June 25, 2019
REVIEW TYPE:	Expedited Review
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Expedited review category # 7

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has APPROVED your submission. This approval is based on an appropriate risk/benefit ratio and a project design wherein the risks have been minimized. All research must be conducted in accordance with this approved submission.

This submission has received Expedited Review based on the applicable federal regulation.

Please make sure that you follow the procedures for informed consent outlined in the APPROVED proposal as required by federal regulations.

Please note that any modification to previously approved materials must be approved by this committee prior to initiation. Please use the appropriate modification forms for this procedure.

All UNANTICIPATED PROBLEMS involving risks to subjects or others and SERIOUS and UNEXPECTED adverse events must be reported promptly to irb@calstatela.edu using the "Adverse Effects Report Form." All federal and sponsor reporting requirements should also be followed.

All NON-COMPLIANCE issues or COMPLAINTS regarding this project must be reported promptly to this office.

This project has been determined to be a project. Based on the risks, this project requires continuing review by this committee on an annual basis. Please use the appropriate forms for this procedure. Your documentation for continuing review must be received with sufficient time for review and continued approval before the expiration date of June 25, 2019.

Please note that all research records must be retained for a minimum of three years after the completion of the project.

APPENDIX F

**EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT STANDARDIZED PROCEDURE:
A DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOL FOR TRIAGE
LEARNING MODULE (POWER POINT)****EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT
STANDARDIZED PROCEDURE:
A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage**

**Katrina Wallace DNP, RN
DNP Project 2019**

PRE-TEST

1. The importance of learning to triage is:
 - a) To help the triage nurse understand the thinking process and problem solving that goes along with assessment of patients presenting to the Emergency Department.
 - b) To help get the patient in the emergency department faster
 - c) Provide the primary care provider with as detailed information as possible including a complete personal and familial medical history.
 - d) To be able to do a complete physical assessment and have the patient complete all diagnostic testing before they can see a primary care provider.
2. Which one is not part of the four categories of the patient interview?
 - a) Symptoms
 - b) Vital Signs
 - c) Medical History
 - d) Marital Status

PRE-TEST CONTINUED

3. Which of these is a subjective finding?
 - a) Fever 102.5F
 - b) Pain 8/10
 - c) Emesis 200 ml
 - d) Tachycardia, HR 114

4. Subjective and Objective findings are not a part of the physical examinations.
 - a) True
 - b) False

5. Some of the seven categories of the problem-solving process involves:
 - a) Possible Diagnosis
 - b) Pathophysiology
 - c) Diagnostic Studies
 - d) All of the above

COURSE OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this module is to provide the triage nurse and other health professionals a clinical approach to accurately and efficiently diagnose common chief complaints in an Emergency Department triage. Information presented are organized in a problem-solving process that includes: Chief complaint, Definition, Symptoms, Pathophysiology, Physical Findings, Diagnostic Studies, Treatments, and Possible Diagnosis.

Upon completion of this module, the learner should be able to:

- ❖ Explain the purpose of this learning module.
- ❖ Discuss the four categories of the patient interview.
- ❖ Differentiate between subjective and objective findings.
- ❖ Discuss key elements of the physical examination.
- ❖ State the seven categories of the problem-solving process.
- ❖ Be able to explain the problem-solving process of two different presenting chief complaints

PURPOSE

- ❖ To educate the triage nurse on the clinical approach to accurately and efficiently identify potential diagnoses of common chief complaints.
- ❖ To facilitate the triage nurse's understanding of the thinking process and problem solving that goes along with assessment of patients presenting to the Emergency Department.
- ❖ To guide the triage nurse in utilizing the new standard protocol that will be implemented in the Emergency Department.

PATIENT INTERVIEW

In order to rule out differential diagnosis, it is important to always gather pertinent information

- ❖ Chief complaint
- ❖ Vital Signs
- ❖ Symptoms
- ❖ Medical History

(Stanfield, 2015)

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

-
❖ Vital Signs.
-
❖ Height & Weight
-
❖ Quick Focused Assessment
-
❖ Subjective Findings
 - ❑ How the patient describes their symptoms; Feelings and perceptions; Pt's story; Pain number.
-
❖ Objective Findings: Data that is observable and measurable
 - ❑ Vital Signs
 - ❑ Head-to-toe Assessment, Physical presentation
-
❖ Use Interview style questions
 - ❑ Direct, simple; Laymen's terminology

(Seller & Symons, 2018)

SAMPLE STANDARD PROCEDURE POLICY

Page No: 1 of 8	Section: 1.0105
Standardized Procedure Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	
Subject: Standardized Procedure Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	Reviewed: 03/16/2011/01/13, 09/14/11/15
Manual: Emergency Department	Revised: 7/12, 11/17
Governing Board Approval	Date: 3/19

POLICY
Approved registered nurses in the Emergency Department may initiate emergency treatment as defined in this policy if a physician is not immediately available.

EDUCATION, TRAINING AND EXPERIENCE
Advanced Cardiac Life Support Provider Status
Initial Evaluation - satisfactory probationary period by Clinical Director or designee
Ongoing Evaluation - annual performance appraisal

SUPERVISION
The procedure will be under the general supervision of the Emergency Department Medical Director. The physical presence of the Medical Director or any physician in the facility is not required.

CRITERIA
Emergency room or other physician is not immediately available.
Upon assessment, a patient in the Emergency Room exhibits signs and symptoms, which require emergent treatment.
PEDS patients are 14 years old or younger.

DOCUMENTATION
Clinical assessment and treatment and response will be entered in the patient's Emergency Room Record

QUALIFIED PERSONNEL
Nurses of qualified Emergency Nurses on file in the office the ICU/ER Director / HR Office

PROCEDURE
Qualified Emergency Room registered nurses may initiate the following treatment for the specific conditions. Obtain Vital Signs initially and PBN according to instructions or clinical needs. Notify the Emergency Room physician as soon as possible:

ANAPHYLAXIS WITH HYPOTENSION / UNSTABLE AIRWAY

MD evaluation immediate:
Cardiac monitoring, continuous
Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
250 mL IV bolus three times of isotonic solution (0.9% saline for adults, and 20cc/kg IV bolus times one for pediatrics. This should be followed by isotonic solution rate 30cc/hour for adults and 15cc/hour for pediatrics. MD reevaluation within one hour.

Subject: Standardized Procedure Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	Page 2 of 7
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RT evaluation: Airway Tach li or bradycardia

Respiratory ED MD order:

ADULT: Give Benadryl 25 mg IV. Have available at bedside: Epinephrine 1:1000, 0.3 mg IM
PEDS: Give Benadryl 1 mg/kg IV. Have available at bedside: Epinephrine 1:1000, 0.01mg/kg subcutaneous (max dose 0.3 mg). See - Adrenaline A for Pediatric dosing chart.

See Symptomatic Hypotension below

SYMPTOMATIC HYPOTENSION

MD evaluation immediate:

Lie patient down. Trendelenburg or leg elevation PEN
Cardiac monitoring, continuous
Continuous O₂ saturation monitoring
Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
If emphysema with hypotension also follow regimen above

ADULT IV fluid challenge:
Except in patients with signs and symptoms of CHF, fluid bolus 250mL normal saline for symptomatic SBP < 90 with HR > 110 when hypotension/oliguria suspect an underlying cause, notify ED MD.

PEDS IV fluid challenge:
50 or 100 mL/kg IV fluid challenge. May repeat twice PEN to maintain systolic BP above 70 = (2 x Kg) up to 100mL/kg, notify ED MD.

New Onset Weak and Dry

- Obtain Fragmented blood glucose
- 12-lead ECG

CHEST PAIN

MD evaluation immediate:

- 12-lead ECG within 10 minutes handed to MD
- 02 per mask or nasal cannula at 2 - 4 L/minute
- If chest pain persists after implementation of above notify ED MD.
- ASA 02 mg PO / ASA 040 mg orally if unable to take or NPO if no contraindications, i.e. bleeding tendencies or ASA allergy or coagulants
- Cardiac monitoring, continuous
- Continuous O₂ saturation monitoring
- Vital Signs initially and PBN according to interventions or clinical needs
- Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)

Subject: Standardized Procedure Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol	Page 3 of 7
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- IV isotonic solution at TCO rate (0.9% saline at 20 mL/hour)
- Lab: CBC, BMP, Magnesium, Troponin, LDI,
- Portable Chest X-ray
- ACLS protocol PEN
- If any medications are given via protocol, the administering nurse will write an order for the medication "per protocol"

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE INFANTS/CHILDREN

- Temperature greater than 100.4
- Acetaminophen 15 mg/kg suppository For Rectum or suspension PO (if none given within 4 hours) AND/OR Ibuprofen 10 mg/kg suspension PO (if none given within 6 hours)
- If core temperature 104° or greater: Notify ED MD and ADD appropriate cooling measures

Notify ED MD:

- Any symptomatic febrile patient
- All children < 90 days with documented core temperature > 100.3
- History of Sickle Cell disease, Immunocompromise, chronic disease (Diabetes)
- Fatigue, anorexia, Pruritus, tachypnea, poor eye contact, complicated birth history

WHEEZING WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

MD evaluation immediate:

Pulse oximetry
Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%)
Blue-saline mask and high flow O₂ ventilatory assist PEN

ALL MEDICATIONS REQUIRE AID ORDER:
Pivoneil (Albuterol) 2.5 mg unit dose and Atrovent 0.5 mg unit dose by aerosol (nebulizer treatment)
Call Respiratory Therapist to assist PEN

ADULT:
If no contraindications to steroids, Decadron (Dexamethasone) 10mg IV push (M if unable to give IV)
If no contraindications to steroids, Decadron 0.6mg/kg IV push up to 10 mg (M if unable to give IV)

PEDS:
If no contraindications to steroids, Decadron 0.6mg/kg IV push up to 10 mg (M if unable to give IV)

RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

MD evaluation immediate:

- Cardiac monitoring, continuous
- Pulse oximetry
- ABG
- Supplemental Oxygen by mask or nasal cannula to optimize SaO₂ (>95%) plus 2-6 cc mask and high flow O₂ ventilatory assist PEN
- 12-lead ECG
- Portable Chest X-ray

PROBLEM-SOLVING PROCESS

In order to determine the patient problem and identify potential diagnoses, the examiner must be able to understand the concept and disease process of the underlying problem. This must be done with the knowledge and understanding of categories below.

Categories are presented and organized in a problem-solving process that includes:

- ❖ Chief complaint
- ❖ Definition
- ❖ Symptoms
- ❖ Pathophysiology
- ❖ Physical Findings
- ❖ Diagnostic Studies
- ❖ Treatment
- ❖ Possible Diagnosis

(Seller & Symons, 2018)

CHIEF COMPLAINTS

- ❖ Anaphylaxis with Hypotension/ Unstable Airway
- ❖ Symptomatic Hypotension
- ❖ Chest Pain
- ❖ Elevated Temperature/ Fever
- ❖ Wheezing with Respiratory Distress
- ❖ Seizures
- ❖ Overdose
- ❖ Fractures and Sprains
- ❖ Head Injury (Traumatic)
- ❖ Vaginal Bleeding
- ❖ Abdominal Pain
- ❖ Weak/ Dizzy and > 60 years of age
- ❖ GI bleeding
- ❖ Urinary Tract Infection
- ❖ Lacerations with Possibility of Foreign Bodies

Note: All categories are chief complaints acquired from a local Emergency Department's *Standardized Procedure: Treatment & Diagnostic Protocol*. Only those categories used in the standard procedure will be addressed along with the diagnostic tests and treatments ordered.

ANAPHYLAXIS WITH HYPOTENSION/ UNSTABLE AIRWAY

- **Definition:** An allergic reaction that is severe, acute and can potentially be life-threatening. Requires immediate medical attention.
- **Symptoms:** Severe dyspnea, swelling and blockage of airway, bronchial constriction, wheezing, angioedema, urticaria, hypotension, stridor and vomiting and diarrhea. Usually occurs within 15 minutes of exposure.
- **Pathophysiology:** Body exposed to certain chemicals or food → antigen stimulates mast cells to release of histamine and other cytokines from mast cells and basophils, causing contraction of both bronchial smooth muscles (bronchoconstriction, vomiting), vasodilation of peripheral vasculature. capillary leak (urticaria and angioedema).
- **Physical Findings:** General appearance: Look for s/s of shock (hypotension, tachycardia), Airway: Swelling, stridor, dyspnea & hoarseness, throat tightness; Respiratory: cough, dyspnea, wheezing, stridor, tachypnea, tongue swelling; Circulation: pale, clammy, palpitations, hypotension; GI: NV, diarrhea, abdominal pain; Neuro: syncope, seizures, unresponsiveness, dizziness anxiety; Dermatologic: urticaria, angioedema, erythema
- **Diagnostic Studies:** Primarily a clinical diagnosis, Cardiac monitoring, pulse oximetry
- **Treatment:** Oxygen (SPO₂>95%), NS 250ml IV Bolus,
- MD order: Benadryl 25mg IV, Epinephrine 1:1000, 0.3mg IM
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Anaphylactic reaction.

(Anaphylaxis, 2019).

SYMPTOMATIC HYPOTENSION

- **Definition:** A blood pressure that is very low, causing symptoms and does not adequately supply enough blood flow to vital organs and the body. Orthostatic Hypotension: Symptoms occurs predominately when the patient goes from a lying or sitting position to a standing position.
- In order to effectively treat hypotension, it is vital to know what the cause is. Hypovolemia (bleeding, dehydration), Shock, Medications (diuretics, HTN meds, narcotics), Diseases (heart problems, endocrine, sepsis)
- Hypotension: BP < 90/60
- Orthostatic Hypotension: decrease in SBP > 20 mm Hg or DBP > 10 mm Hg when going from lying or sitting to a standing position within 3 minutes.
- **Symptoms:** dizziness, lightheadedness, syncope, weakness, blurry vision, nausea, fatigue
- **Pathophysiology:** Orthostatic Hypotension: Change in position from lying or sitting to standing causes a shift in blood to pool in the lower extremities, causing a reduction in filling pressure of the right atrium, causing a decrease in cardiac output and arterial pressure and a drop-in blood pressure. Hypovolemic Shock: Hypovolemia causing a decrease in venous return, causing a decrease in preload which then decreases cardiac output leading to hypotension. Severe hypotension can lead to tissue hypoxia and perfusion failure causing organ dysfunction and ultimately multiorgan failure.

(Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018)

SYMPTOMATIC HYPOTENSION CONTINUED

- **Physical Findings:** (Hypovolemic Shock) General appearance: Weak, fatigue; Neuro: Confusion, lack of concentration, dizzy lightheadedness; Respiratory: Rapid, shallow breathing; Cardiac: Tachycardia; Circulation: rapid pulse; GI: Abdomen/epigastric area: NV; Dermatologic: Cold, clammy, pale skin
 - **Diagnostic Studies:** If new onset of weak and dizzy, obtain Blood glucose finger stick and EKG
 - **Treatment:** Supine or Trendelenburg position or BLE elevate pm, Oxygen (SPO2>95%), NS 250ml IV Bolus Fluid challenge (except CHF), or with SBP<100 with HR> 110 when suspected dehydration. Cardiac monitoring, POX
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Diagnosis is usually the cause of the hypotension.
 - **Decrease Cardiac output:** Hypovolemia, Dehydration, Orthostatic Hypotension, hemorrhage,
 - **Decrease Contractility:** MI, CHF, arrhythmias, drugs, electrolytes
 - **Obstruction:** PE, tension pneumothorax
 - **Decrease in Systemic Vasculature Resistance:** Sepsis, anaphylaxis, vasodilators

(Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018)

CHEST PAIN

- **Definition:** A discomfort felt along your body (anterior chest) between the neck and abdomen. Pain can be sharp, crushing, tightness, heaviness, dull, or ache.
 - **Symptoms:** Pain radiates to arm, neck, back or shoulders. Can worsen with exertion. Abnormal VS (ST, SB, tachypnea, hypotension), SOB, signs of hypoperfusion (confusion, cyanotic/ashen color, diaphoresis), hypoxemia, abnormal BS or heart sounds
- **Pathophysiology:** Visceral fibers enters the spinal cord and provide input through the heart, lungs, esophagus and great vessels creating painful stimulus from any of the organs. Because the dorsal fibers overlap, the pain stimulus can be perceived as originating from the thoracic area called referred pain.

(Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018; Sellar & Symons, 2018)

CHEST PAIN CONTINUED

- **Physical Findings:** Examine the five characteristics of the pain (location, intensity, radiating, quality, duration) and anything that worsens or alleviates the pain.
- **General appearance:** Check for pallor, diaphoresis, cyanosis, anxiety, fatigue. **Respiratory:** Asses lung sounds for s/s of congestion (rales, rhonchi), pleural friction rubs and effusion. The chest is examined for trauma, palpated for crepitus and tenderness. **Cardiac:** Heart sounds should be assessed for intensity, S1S2, murmurs, pericardial friction rubs, and gallops. **GI:** Abdomen/ epigastric area: Palpated for pain, distention, and masses. **Circulation:** BLE are inspected for edema, pulses, signs of DVT and pulses. **Pain:** Can be exacerbated by exercise and physical or emotional stress. Women has atypical chest pains (NV, dizziness, weakness).
- **Diagnostic Studies:** EKG within 3 minutes, CBC, BMP, Mg, Troponin, LDL, Portable Chest X-R,
- **Treatment:** Oxygen 2-4L NC, (SPO2>95%), ASA 324mg if no contradictions, Cardiac monitoring, POX
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Always rule out life-threatening causes first. **Cardiac:** Ischemic, Non-ischemic: Angina, AMI, ACS, aortic dissection, pericarditis. **Noncardiac:** GI: GERD, ulcers; **Pulmonary:** PE, PNA, **Musculoskeletal:** Trauma, costochondritis, **Dermatologic:** Herpes Zoster (Shingles)

(Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018; Seller & Symo.

QUIZ

1. For symptomatic hypotension with new onset weakness and dizziness, all are pertinent diagnostic tests or treatments except:
 - a. Trendelenburg position
 - b. Normal Saline IV Bolus
 - c. 12 Lead EKG
 - d. ABG
2. A patient complaining of chest pain can have all the possible diagnosis except:
 - a. Pulmonary Embolism
 - b. Orthostatic Hypotension
 - c. Heartburn
 - d. Non-Ischemic Angina

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE/ FEVER

- **Definition:** Fever is a temperature greater than 100.4°F, frequently a symptom of an underlying medical condition. Usually a s/s of an infection, however there can be non- infectious causes of fever.
 - **Symptoms:** The s/s is usually related to the cause of the fever (rash, cough, sore throat, UTI, infection, drowsy, etc.) Most common s/s are skin warm or hot, flushed, shaking chills. There also can be no s/s except the fever itself.
 - **Pathophysiology:** Exogenous pyrogens (microbes) can cause fevers by triggering the hypothalamic thermoregulatory center and raising the hypothalamic set point. This causes vasoconstriction and shunting of blood from the peripheral extremities to decrease heat loss. In order to increase heat production, shivering is produced.
- This continues until a new set point is reached and the hypothalamic is reset with a decreased temperature (by cooling measures or antipyretic medications) which starts the heat loss process through vasodilation and sweating.
- **Physical Findings:** Variable, depending on the cause of the fever; also, can have no other physical findings except the fever.
 - **Diagnostic Studies:** Not specified in standard protocol.
 - **Treatment:** Acetaminophen or Ibuprofen, cooling measures
 - **Possible Diagnosis:** Multiple, will depend on other s/s and assessments. Can also have fever of unknown origin

WHEEZING WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

- **Definition:** A high-pitched whistling sound upon inspiration and/or expiration of air movement through the narrowing of the airways; usually accompanied by respiratory distress (dyspnea, sob, accessory muscle use, intercostal retractions, pursed lip breathing, agitation, cyanosis, decreased level of consciousness) or dyspnea and sob.
 - **Symptoms:** Dyspnea, sob, accessory muscle use, intercostal retractions, pursed lip breathing, agitation, cyanosis, decreased level of consciousness
 - **Pathophysiology:** Wheezing: Reflex bronchoconstriction causes a narrowing of the airway, therefore air movement upon inspiration and/or expiration can cause turbulent and vibrations of the bronchial walls; this vibration causes the wheezing. The narrowing of the airway walls can lead to decreased alveolar perfusion causing hypoxemia and hypocapnia and therefore causing respiratory distress (dyspnea and sob).
 - Respiratory Distress: Irritant and J receptor stimulation causes hyperventilation and SOB
 - **Physical Findings:** Respiratory: Assessment of lung sounds will show inspiratory and/or expiratory wheezing. Cardio: tachycardia
 - **Diagnostic Studies:** ABG, EKG, PCxR, Cardiac monitoring, POX
 - **Treatment:** Oxygen (SPO₂>95%), Albuterol 2.5mg unit dose and Atrovent 0.5mg unit dose Nebulizer treatment. MD order: Dexamethasone 10mg IVP/IM
 - **With Respiratory Distress Treatment:** Bag-Valve-Mask high flow O₂ ventilatory assist prn (Call RT), ABG, Oxygen (SPO₂>95%), PCXR, EKG,
 - **Possible Diagnosis:** Acute asthma attack, Reoccurring wheezing with a history of asthma, COPD or CHF is indicative of an exacerbation episode.
- (Seller & Symons, 2018; Ignatavicius, Workman & Rebar, 2018).

SEIZURES

- **Definition:** A sudden convulsion from a disruption of electrical activity in the brain causing uncontrolled muscle movements (jerking) of the body or extremities with a temporary loss of consciousness.
- **Symptoms:** A momentary loss of muscle control of rigidity and/or jerking movements (tonic/clonic) followed by a brief period of loss of consciousness followed by confusion and/or hallucinations, garbled speech and the inability to recall the occurrence.
- **Pathophysiology:** Seizures occur when there is a sudden electrical imbalance in the brain. The imbalance occurs between the excitatory and inhibitory forces in the network of cortical neurons causing a sudden excitability.
- **Physical Findings:** Neuro: Depending on where the cortex is affected, it then causes the manifestation of symptoms. A single cortical neuron can be discharged, causing a focal, or partial seizure affecting only one part of a limb or face. When both sides of the brain have electrical imbalance, the seizure manifests into generalized whole body seizure, known as general tonic-clonic seizures
- **Diagnostic Studies:** Core temperature, Blood glucose
- **Treatment:** Seizure precautions, Lorazepam IV Push, (IM if unable to obtain IV), Repeat in 10 – 15 minutes if seizure does not subside.
- **Possible & Differential Diagnosis:** Seizures

(Seizures, 2019; Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018)

OVERDOSE

- **Definition:** An accidental or intentional ingestion and overuse of a prescribed or non-prescribed substance.
- **Symptoms:** Variations in vital signs (high and low), coma, lethargy, diaphoresis, seizures, chest pains, abdominal pain, NVD,
- **Pathophysiology:** Specific drugs affects different organs therefore symptoms can vary.
- **Physical Findings:** Can vary depending on the drug. See symptoms.
- **Diagnostic Studies & Treatments:** : Blood glucose, Urine toxicology screen, Cardiac monitoring, POX
- **Treatment:** Oxygen (SPO₂>95%), Contact Poison Control, Suicide precautions, Restraints per policy. Charcoal 1gm/kg po (50% with Sorbitol and 50% plain charcoal). if patient alert and able to tolerate oral with intact gag reflex. Mix with water, juice, soda prn.
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Drug overdose, prescription versus non- prescription

(Overdose, 2019; Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018)

QUIZ

1. There are times when there are no signs and symptoms for fever, except the fever itself.
 - a. True
 - b. False

2. A momentary loss of muscle control of rigidity and/or jerking movements (tonic/clonic) followed by a brief period of loss of consciousness followed by confusion and/or hallucinations, garbled speech and the inability to recall the occurrence is most likely:
 - a. Stroke
 - b. Parkinson
 - c. Seizure
 - d. Drug Overdose

FRACTURES AND SPRAINS

- **Definition:** A break or disturbance in the continuity of a bone anywhere in the body, at any age, that causes pain, discomforts and affects mobility of the area.
- **Symptoms:** Complete fracture- break goes across width of bone so that bone is divided in 2 sections.
- Incomplete fracture- fracture involves only part of the bone and does not divide the bone into 2 sections; is not displaced.
- **Pathophysiology Bone Healing:** The five stages of a healing fracture consists of: 1) 24-72 hours: A hematoma is formed, 2) 3 days – 2 weeks: granulation begins forming fibrocartilage 3) Vascular and cellular proliferation creating new vasculature called Callus formation 4) 3-8 weeks: Callus is reabsorbed and transformed into bone 5) 4wks – up to 1 year consolidation and remodeling of bone begins for healing.
- **Physical Findings:** Ortho: In complete fractures, the bone alignment can be shifted making it a displaced fracture. Incomplete fractures are not displaced. Other findings can be swelling, numbness, tingling and pain at the sight,
- **Diagnostic Studies:** X-Ray of affected extremity/ area.
- **Treatments:** Immobilize effected extremity, elevation, ice, C-Spine for neck pain/injury, Ibuprofen or Tylenol for pain
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Various depending on symptoms and place of injury.

(Ignatavicius, Workman, & Rebar, 2018)

HEAD INJURY (TRAUMA)

- **Definition:** Trauma, injury or blow to the head that can alter mental and physical function. A closed head injury is when the injury does not break your skull. An open or penetrating head injury is one where something breaks the skull and enters the brain.
 - **Symptoms:** headache pain, dizziness, NV. Confusion, Ringing in ears, Loss of consciousness, seizures, loss of muscle control,
 - MD evaluate immediately if loss of consciousness, altered mental status, vomiting x 3 or more since injury, and severe HA
 - **Pathophysiology:** Depending on type and severity of injury. Skull changes are common, can be simple linear fracture to complicated depressed , in which bone fragments pushes beneath the calvarias surface.
- Point of impact can cause intracranial bleeding, intracerebral focal contusion or extra- cellular hemorrhage. Subdural hemorrhages can be caused by tearing of veins, or disruption from cortical arteries.
- **Physical Findings:** Neuro: Glasgow Coma Scale score, bruising or bleeding on head and/or scalp, blood in ear canal, cranial nerve VI palsy may indicate intracranial pressure, CN VII palsy may indicate fracture of the temporal bone, decreased hearing or hearing loss,
 - **Diagnostic Studies:** Notify MD immediately if need a CT scan. Cardiac monitoring, POX if severe.
 - **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
 - **Possible Diagnosis:** Concussions, Skull fractures, Scalp wounds, Intracerebral Hemorrhage, subarachnoid Hemorrhage, Hematoma, Brain edema, Diffuse axonal injury

(Head Trauma, 2018; Seller & Symons, 2018)

VAGINAL BLEEDING

- **Definition:** Vaginal bleeding occurring before menarche or after menopause, is considered abnormal. It can vary in amount of bleeding and its pattern of bleeding.
 - **Symptoms:** Red blood on underwear, pelvic or abdominal pain or fullness, excessive pain when menstruating.
 - **Pathophysiology:** A disturbance in the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis is the result of Anovulatory dysfunctional uterine bleeding. A proliferation of the endometrium persists because ovulation is not occurring. Therefore, there is no production of progesterone to stabilize the endometrium. Uterine bleeding dysfunctions results from changes in prostaglandin concentrations, increased endometrial responsiveness to vasodilating prostaglandins as well as changes in endometrial vascular structure.
- **Physical Findings:** GYN: Copious vaginal bleeding: Bright red hemorrhage with clots, a darker tint of blood, vaginal secretions, enlarged uterus, GU: urinary frequency or urgency,
 - **Diagnostic Studies:** Urine pregnancy test, if negative → CBC
 - If positive → CBC, Type and Rh, Quantitative beta HCG (if < 12 weeks gestation), Pelvic Ultrasound
 - **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
 - **Possible Diagnosis:** Uterine fibroids, menopause, PID, Pregnancy complications, fibromyomas, ovarian endometriosis, IUD, cervical carcinoma, uterine tumors. During Pregnancy: Placenta previa and abruptio placentae.

(Vaginal Bleed, 2019; Seller & Symons, 2018; Estephan & Sinet, 2018)

ABDOMINAL PAIN

- **Definition:** Pain that is originated from the organs inside the abdominal cavity including: stomach, colon, pancreas, spleen, gallbladder, liver, appendix. Obtaining patient history, Location of the pain, and pattern is a very important key in determining the cause and can help with diagnosing the problem
- **Symptoms:** Pain, bloating, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, fever, melena, jaundice, dark urine
- **Pathophysiology:** Abdominal pain can be caused by inflammation, by distention of an organ, or loss of blood supply to an organ. However, it can be caused for an unspecified reason as well. Pathophysiology will depend on the disease process of the diagnosis.
- **Physical Findings:** Assessments of findings can provide further information of the problem: GI: Location of tenderness, positive occult blood, bowel sounds, signs of inflammation, presence of mass.
- **Diagnostic Studies:**
- **Epigastric & Upper abdominal pain:** CBC, CMP, Lipase, UA, and EKG if >40 years old)
- **Lower abdominal pain:** CBC, BMP, UA, UCG (females who can menstruate)
- **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Cholecystitis, Appendicitis, Gastritis, Bowel Obstruction, Constipation, Peptic Ulcer, esophagitis, Peritonitis, Irritable Bowel, Gastroenteritis, Acute Diverticulitis, Kidney Stone, Gallstones, Hepatitis. Acute Pancreatitis,

(Abdominal Pain, 2019; Sellar & Symons, 2018)

QUIZ

1. An incomplete fracture involves a break that goes across the width of a bone so that bone is divided in two sections.
 - a. True
 - b. False
2. With any abdominal pain, obtaining patient history, location of the pain, and pattern is a very important key in determining the cause and can help with diagnosing the problem.
 - a. True
 - b. False

GENERAL WEAKNESS AND DIZZY > 60 YEARS OF AGE

Dizzy

- **Definition:** A sensation of lightheadedness, disequilibrium commonly accompanied by gait imbalance; can also be a near fainting.
- **Symptoms:** Lightheadedness, feeling of wanting to faint, unsteadiness, loss of balance, NV.
- **Pathophysiology:** The Vestibular system (inner ear, CN VIII, vestibular nuclei in brain stem and cerebellum) is involved in balance. Sense of balance is from the visual input from the eyes and proprioceptive input from the peripheral nerve, along with the cerebral cortex receiving output from the lower centers and integrates information to produce the perception of motion.
- **Physical Findings:** General: Fatigue, tiredness, Neuro: lightheadedness, orthostatic hypotension, EENT: Nystagmus, ear infection, Cardio: heart rhythm abnormalities,
- **Diagnostic Studies:** CBC, BMP, D-Dimer, Troponin, UA, PCXR, EKG
- **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Vertigo, Drug effects, Hypoglycemia, Oxygenation problems, Meniere's disease, Orthostatic Hypotension, Neurologic problems, Cardiac Arrhythmias, Muscle disorders,

(Dizziness, 2019a; Dizziness, 2019b; General Weakness, 2019)

GENERAL WEAKNESS AND DIZZY CONTINUED

General Weakness

- **Definition:** A generalized feeling of decrease muscle strength throughout the body.
- **Symptoms:** difficult to do tasks depends on what muscles are affected; due to lack of energy, problems with balancing and gait. Symptoms associated can be double vision, alteration in sensation such as numbness and tingling.
- **Pathophysiology:** Disruption of brain signals or impulses through the sensory nerve pathway or motor nerve pathway to the muscles. This can be along the spinal cord, crossing the synapses, to the nerve cell, up the spinal cord to the thalamus over to the cortex of the cerebrum where impulses are received and information interpreted from the sensory receptors to elicit a movement via an impulse.
- **Pathophysiology continue:** The disruption can also be after the impulse is elicited, where it travels back down the spinal cord, crosses the synapse between the nerve fibers in the spinal cord and a motor nerve to the neuromuscular junction where the impulse crosses from motor nerve to receptors on the motor end plate of the muscles, where it stimulates the muscle to move. General weakness can be a result of any disruption in the pathway of the a brain, spinal cord, nerves, muscles or any of the connections is damaged or diseased.
- **Diagnostic Studies:** CBC, BMP, D-Dimer, Troponin, UA, PCXR, EKG
- **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Orthostatic Hypotension, Neurologic problems, Cardiac Arrhythmias, Muscle disorders

(Dizziness, 2019a; Dizziness, 2019b; General Weakness,

GI BLEEDING

- **Definition:** Bleeding that can occur anywhere along the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, from mouth to anus. Blood maybe seen by the naked eye via emesis, usually indicating upper GI tract bleeding, or blood in stools, which usually indicates lower GI bleed.
- **Symptoms:** Diaphoretic, Palpitations, Abdominal pain, NV, Diarrhea with bloody stools, dizziness, general weakness
- **Pathophysiology:**
- **Hematemesis:** Coffee ground emesis resulting from GI bleed that has slowed down or stopped with the conversion of red Hb to brown hematin by gastric acid.
- **Hematochezia:** Gross blood passing through GI track to rectum with rapid flow of blood through the intestines.
- **Melena:** Black, tarry stools that suggests upper GI bleeding or within the small bowels; Or blood that has been held in GI tract after the bleeding has stopped.
- **Physical Findings:** Neuro: Syncope, Cardio: Tachycardia, Orthostatic Hypotension, Hypovolemia, Hypovolemic Shock (Severe) GI: Abdominal Pain, Distention, Anemia (Pallor, Diaphoresis), Positive Occult Blood, Active Rectal Bleeding
- **Diagnostic Studies:**
Significant rectal bleed, active, melena or hematemesis: CBC, BMP, PT/ PTT/ INR
Scant rectal bleeding or spotting: CBC
- **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol.
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Drug induced GI bleed, Chronic Liver Disease
- **Upper GI Bleed:** Peptic Ulcers, erosions of esophagus, stomach or duodenum, esophageal varices, gastritis
- **Lower GI Bleed:** Polyps, Diverticular diseases, hemorrhoids, Inflammatory bowel disease, Colon cancer, Colitis, Anal fissures (Gastrointestinal Bleed. 2019)

URINARY TRACT INFECTION

- **Definition:** An infection of the urinary system, either the urethra (Urethritis, Acute Urethral Syndrome), bladder, (Cystitis), or kidneys (Pyelonephritis) usually with a bacterium; it can develop to become systemic.
- **Symptoms:** Dysuria, frequency, Fever, Burning or painful voiding small amount of urine, hematuria, back pain, or can be asymptomatic.
- **Pyelonephritis-** UTI symptoms along with flank pain, fever, chills, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain,
- Elderly patients or patients with neurogenic bladder or indwelling catheter can have signs and symptoms of sepsis (tachycardia, tachypnea, hypotension, high fevers) and delirium, confusion and not have UTI symptoms.
- **Pathophysiology:** When bacteria (most common is Escherichia coli bacteria) ascends to the bladder along the urethra and in pyelonephritis, ascend the ureter into the kidneys.
- **Physical Findings:** GU: Hematuria, Dysuria,
- **Pyelonephritis:** Flank pain, Costovertebral angle percussion tenderness at affected side. Enlarged kidney sometimes palpable.
- **Diagnostic Studies:** Urinalysis, Urine Culture
- **Treatment:** Not specified in standard protocol
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Urinary Tract Infection, Urethritis, Cystitis, Acute Pyelonephritis,

(Urinary Tract Infection, 2019; Sellar & Symons, 2018)

LACERATIONS WITH POSSIBILITY OF FOREIGN BODIES

- **Definition:** A cut or tear on the tissue (laceration), abrasions or puncture wounds can be caused by multiple mechanisms. Wounds can involve injury to the tendons, nerves or blood vessels. Foreign bodies are materials that can remain inside the wound, such as glass, splinter, clothing, dirt etc. and can be a source of infection to the wound, therefore should always be removed. Laceration most commonly are cleansed and sutured to prevent dirt and bacteria from staying in the wound.
- **Symptoms:** Pain at site, loss of sensation, numbness and tingling if injury involves damage to nerve, weakness if injury involves tendons; Redness, swelling if wound becomes infected.
- **Pathophysiology of Healing:** Healing starts immediately after an injury. WBCs and coagulation starts with the release of neutrophils and macrophages to begin debridement of the tissues and bacteria.
- Epithelialization start as the cells migrate to the wound edges going across the wound forming a protective barrier on the wound in 12 -24 hours. Then scar formation starts as collagen remodeling occurs and scar becomes thinner and loses its redness.
- **Physical Findings:** Visible bleeding at site of wound, Associated injuries can involve tendon, bone, nerve, vascular, joints, and foreign bodies can depend on mechanism of injury and dictate the physical findings such as numbness, tingling, loss of sensation, pain, decreased movement to area of wound, redness, and swelling,
- **Diagnostic Studies:** X-Ray soft tissue of affected area
- **Treatment:** Cleanse of wound, removal of foreign body
- **Possible Diagnosis:** Lacerations, Foreign Body Removal

(Laceration and Foreign Bodies, 2019)

QUIZ

1. Hematochezia is the passage of gross blood from the rectum, usually indicates lower GI bleeding but may result from which of the following?
 - a. Vigorous upper GI bleeding with rapid flow of blood through the intestines.
 - b. Coffee-ground emesis indicating the bleeding has stopped.
 - c. Black-tarry stools typically from a lower GI bleed and ingestion of iron.
 - d. An indicator that shows the patient is in hypovolemic shock.
2. A patient with the symptoms of dysuria, fever, flank pain, and chills suggests which condition?
 - a. Gonorrhea
 - b. Prostatitis
 - c. Pyelonephritis
 - d. Low back pain

CONCLUSION

This electronic self-learning module has been provided to train the triage nurses the clinical approach for identifying potential diagnosis of patients. It is to help the nurses understand the process of patient assessments: Interview, physical exam, and understanding the problem-solving process. Information learned will be put into practice with the new standard protocol that will soon be initiated at triage in the Emergency Department.

POST-TEST

1. The importance of learning to triage is:
 - a) To help the triage nurse understand the thinking process and problem solving that goes along with assessment of patients presenting to the Emergency Department.
 - b) To help get the patient in the emergency department faster
 - c) Provide the primary care provider with as detailed information as possible including a complete personal and familial medical history.
 - d) To be able to do a complete physical assessment and have the patient complete all diagnostic testing before they can see a primary care provider.
2. Which one is not part of the four categories of the patient interview?
 - a) Symptoms
 - b) Vital Signs
 - c) Medical History
 - d) Marital Status

**POST-TEST
CONTINUED**

3. Which of these is a subjective finding?
 - a) Fever 102.5F
 - b) Pain 8/10
 - c) Emesis 200 ml
 - d) Tachycardia, HR 114

4. Subjective and Objective findings are not a part of the physical examinations.
 - a) True
 - b) False

5. Some of the seven categories of the problem-solving process involves:
 - a) Possible Diagnosis
 - b) Pathophysiology
 - c) Diagnostic Studies
 - d) All of the above

COURSE EVALUATION

Please mark your answer on a separate paper provided and turn in.	Strongly Disagree			Strongly Agree	
1. The course content was clear and presented in a logical manner.	1	2	3	4	5
2. The course material was informative and thorough.	1	2	3	4	5
1. This information learned in this course helps improve my role as a triage nurse.	1		3	4	5
2. The length and timing of the course was appropriate to the topic of study.	1	2	3	4	5
5. The course content was congruent with the course learning objectives.	1	2	3	4	5
6. After taking this course, I am more confident about this subject.	1	2	3	4	5
7. I prefer taking this course online rather than in a classroom.	1	2	3	4	5
8. This e-learning teaching style was appropriate for the course subject	1	2	3	4	5
9. The e-learning course was easy to navigate with on the computer.	1	2	3	4	5
10. I liked the e-learning course.	1	2	3	4	5

REFERENCES

- Abdominal Pain. (2019). MedicineNet. Retrieved from https://www.medicinenet.com/abdominal_pain_pictureslideshow/article.htm
- Anaphylaxis (2019) MedlinePlus. Retrieved from <https://medlineplus.gov/anaphylaxis.html>
- Dizziness. (2019). emedicinehealth. Retrieved from <https://www.emedicinehealth.com/dizziness/article.htm>
- Dizziness. (2019). Merck Manual: Professional Version. Retrieved from [http://www.merckmanuals.com](http://www.merckmanuals.com/dizziness)
- Estephan, A., and Sinet, R. H. (2018). Abnormal (Dysfunctional) uterine bleeding in emergency medicine. Medscape. Retrieved from <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/795587-overview#a5>
- Head Trauma. (2019). Medscape. Retrieved from <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/1163653-overview#a5>
- Ignatavicius, D. D., Workman M. L., & Rebar, C. R., (2018). *Medical-surgical nursing* (9th ed.) St. Louis, MO: Elsevier
- Gastrointestinal Bleed. (2019). Merck Manual: Professional Version. Retrieved from [http://www.merckmanuals.com](http://www.merckmanuals.com/gastrointestinal-bleed)

REFERENCES CONTINUED

- General Weakness. (2019a). MedicineNet. Retrieved from <https://www.medicinenet.com/weakness/symptoms.htm>
- General Weakness. (2019b). Merck Manual: Professional Version. Retrieved from [http://www.merckmanuals.com](http://www.merckmanuals.com/weakness)
- Laceration and Foreign Bodies. (2019). Merck Manual: Professional Version. Retrieved from [http://www.merckmanuals.com](http://www.merckmanuals.com/laceration-and-foreign-bodies)
- Overdose. (2019). emedicinehealth. Retrieved from <https://www.emedicinehealth.com/drugoverdose/article.htm#whatisadrugoverdose>
- Seller, R. H., & Symons, A. B (2018). *Differential diagnosis of common complaints*. (7th ed.) Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier.
- Seizures (2019). MedlinePlus. Retrieved from <https://medlineplus.gov/ency/article/003200.htm>
- Urinary Tract Infections. (2019). Merck Manual: Professional Version. Retrieved from [http://www.merckmanuals.com](http://www.merckmanuals.com/urinary-tract-infections)
- Vaginal Bleed. (2019). emedicinehealth. Retrieved from <https://www.emedicinehealth.com/search/emh/vaginal%20bleeding>

APPENDIX G

ELECTRONIC SELF-LEARNING MODULE CRITIQUES

Thank you for taking my ELM course. I would appreciate your feed-back for a run through before this learning module is released to the learners.

Name: RP

Title: Education Manager, MSN, RN

Date: 03/04/2019

1.	Is the course content clear and arranged in a logical manner?	Y
2.	Does the learning module flow well?	Y
3.	Does the content reflect the learning objectives?	Y
4.	Is the module set-up easy for the learner to understand, easy to ad and navigate through?	Y
5.	Does the learning module content provide enough information for the learner to be able to perform their role of a triage nurse?	Y
6.	This e-learning teaching style was appropriate for the course subject.	Y
7.	The length and timing of the course was appropriate to the topic of study.	Y
8	Did you like this ELM?	Y
9.	How long did it take you to complete the module?	55 min
10.	Please provide two points on what you like about the ELM. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There was a lot of information for the nurse to understand the triage process 2. Easy to follow 	
11.	Please provide two points where improvements can be made/modified. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I would look at different wording in the purpose....all 3 start with "to help" 2. Chief Complaints: How were those diagnoses determined...maybe explain that 	

ELECTRONIC SELF-LEARNING MODULE CRITIQUE

Thank you for taking my ELM course. I would appreciate your feed-back for a run through before this learning module is released to the learners.

Name: RT

Title: Education Manager, MSN, RN, CNOR, RN-BC

Date: 03/10/2019

1.	Is the course content clear and arranged in a logical manner?	Y
2.	Does the learning module flow well?	Y
3.	Does the content reflect the learning objectives?	Y
4.	Is the module set-up easy for the learner to understand, easy to read and navigate through?	Y
5.	Does the learning module content provide enough information for the learner to be able to perform their role of a triage nurse?	Y
6.	This e-learning teaching style was appropriate for the course subject.	Y
7.	The length and timing of the course was appropriate to the topic of study.	Y
8.	Did you like this ELM?	Y
9.	How long did it take you to complete the module?	1.5 hour
10.	Please provide two points on what you like about the ELM. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I learned basic triage skills. 2. I learned about physiology about disease processes 	
11.	Please provide two points where improvements can be made/ modified. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Slide may have too much content; suggest bigger font 2. Suggest more basic “stroke” identification (may be included in neuro 	

APPENDIX H

APPLICATION FOR CONTINUING EDUCATION PROVIDER

BUSINESS, CONSUMER SERVICES, AND HOUSING AGENCY • GOVERNOR EDMUND G. BROWN JR.

BOARD OF REGISTERED NURSING
 PO Box 944210, Sacramento, CA 94244-2100
 P (916) 322-3350 F (916) 574-8637 | www.rn.ca.gov
 Louise R. Bailey, MEd, RN, Executive Officer

**APPLICATION FOR APPROVAL AS A
 CONTINUING EDUCATION PROVIDER
 FEE \$500**

FOR OFFICE USE ONLY

Be sure to complete the entire application, including the Course Information and Instructor Information forms. **Please type or print all entries.**

Provider No: _____

Cashier No: _____

Approval Period: _____

1. Provider/Business Name: XXXX

2. Phone No: Bus:

Res: XXXX

3. Address: XXXX

City: XXXX

State: CA

ZIP Code: XXXX

4. Have you ever been a provider of continuing education for nurses in California?

Yes No

If yes, Provider Name: n/a

Provider No: n/a

5. Provider as a/an:

Association

Corporation

Government Agency

 Individual

Non-Profit Corporation

Partnership

Organized Health Care System

University, College or School

6. Contact Person:

Name: XXXX

Phone No: XXXX

7. Tax ID Number: Select the one that applies and enter that number:

 U.S. Social Security No. or Individual Tax ID Number (SSN/ITIN): XXXX**OR**

Federal Employer Identification No. (FEIN):

8. Individual Responsible for Record Keeping: Thoa Wallace

9. Address of Record Storage:

XXXX

Phone No:

XXXX

I certify under penalty of perjury under the laws of the State of California that I have read and understand the regulations in Article 5, Title 16, California Code of Regulations, and that all courses and instructors meet the requirements of those regulations.

Signature: XXXX

Date: _____

<p>1. TITLE: Emergency Department Standardized Procedure: A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage</p>	<p>2. DATE TO BE OFFERED: TBD</p>
<p>OBJECTIVES (Behavioral Terminology):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the purpose of this learning module. • Discuss the four categories of the patient interview. • Differentiate between subjective and objective findings. • Discuss key elements of the physical examination. • State the seven categories of the problem-solving process. • Be able to explain the problem-solving process of two different presenting complaints. 	
<p>4. OVERVIEW/DESCRIPTION:</p> <p>The learner will be presented with the purpose of the learning module along with patient interview slide that details the information that needs to be gathered from the patient upon triage. Another slide will provide pertinent information on the physical examination and what is subjective versus objective findings. A copy of the Standard Protocol Policy is provided on one slide for the learner to be familiar with it. Following this is the core of the teachings where chief complaint categories are presented and organized in a problem-solving process that includes: Chief complaint, Definition, Symptoms, Pathophysiology, Physical Findings, Diagnostic Studies, and Possible Diagnosis (total of 15 slides for this section). Quizzes to emphasize key points are placed sporadically throughout the learning module. A pre-posttest is given as well to evaluate learner comprehension. A course evaluation is given to the learner upon completion of the learning module.</p>	
<p>5. TYPE OF OFFERING (Academic, Workshop, In-service, Independent study, etc.):</p> <p>Online Power Point, Independent study</p>	
<p>6. TEACHING METHODS:</p> <p>Online teaching module using Power Point; Self-home study for healthcare professionals that wants to learn about using a standard protocol to triage Emergency Department patients.</p>	
<p>7. NUMBER OF CONTACT HOURS: * One contact hour is equivalent to 50 minutes of lecture. This learning module is 1.5 hours or 90 minutes lecture, making it 1.8 contact hours.</p>	

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COURSE INFORMATION

(California Code of Regulations, Title 16, Section 1456)

Please Type or Print All Entries

PROVIDER/BUSINESS NAME: XXXX

8. CONTENT (Outline Form):

Course Objectives.

- ⌘ **Purpose**
- ⌘ **Patient Interview**
 - Chief complaint
 - Vital Signs
 - Medical History
 - Symptoms
- ⌘ **Physical examination**
 - Vital Signs
 - Height & Weight
 - Quick Focused Assessment
 - Subjective Findings
 - Objective Findings
 - Use Interview style questions:
- ⌘ **Sample Standard Procedure Policy**
- ⌘ **Problem-solving process**
 - Chief complaint
 - Definition
 - Symptoms
 - Pathophysiology
 - Physical Findings

- Diagnostic Studies
- Possible Diagnosis

⌘ Chief Complaints

- Anaphylaxis with Hypotension/ Unstable Airway
- Symptomatic Hypotension
- Chest Pain
- Elevated Temperature/ Fever
- Wheezing with Respiratory Distress
- Seizures
- Overdose
- Fractures and Sprains
- Head Injury (Traumatic)
- Vaginal Bleeding
- Abdominal Pain
- Weak/ Dizzy and > 60 years of age
- GI bleeding
- Urinary Tract Infection
- Lacerations with
Possibility of Foreign Bodies

Conclusion

⌘ Course evaluation

- Quizzes are placed at various areas amongst the module.

9. METHOD OF EVALUATION WHEN REQUIRED:

- Pre/Post-survey questionnaire
- Independent study providers describe methodology used to determine number of contact hours.

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1. NAME: XXXX		2a. LICENSE NUMBER: XXXX		
		2b. Date of Expiration: XXXX		
		2c. Type of License: RN		
3. EDUCATION:				
College/University	Major	Degree	Area of Preparation	Year Degree Granted
XXXX	Nursing	ADN	Nursing	XXXX
XXXX	Nursing	BSN	Nursing	XXXX
XXXX	Nursing	MSN	Nursing	XXXX
4. EXPERIENCE: (Start with most recent experience)				
	Position	Clinical Area	From To Mo/Yr Mo/Yr	
XXXX	RN	Emergency Dept	XXXX	
XXXX	RN	Critical Care	XXXX	
XXXX	RN	Emergency Dept	XXXX	
XXXX	RN	Emergency Dept	XXXX	
5. TEACHING EXPERIENCE:				
Title of Course	Description		Month/Year	
6. Have you ever had a course in Principles of Adult Education? Yes No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> If yes, give dates: n/a				

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BOARD OF REGISTERED NURSING

Louise R. Bailey, MEd, RN, Executive Officer

CONTINUING EDUCATION PROVIDER CHECKLIST

The following checklist may help you to be sure your application packet is complete. This will facilitate the timely processing of your application. Check to make sure you have:

4. Typed or clearly block-printed the application.
5. Completed every question on both the "Course Information" and "Instructor Information" page.
6. Indicated the FEIN (if you represent a corporation, health facility, governmental agency, etc.) or
U.S. SSN if you are filing your application as a private citizen in box #7 on the first page of the application.
1. Included a sample of the advertising flyer/brochure and the certificate of completion.
2. Signed and dated the application.
3. Enclosed a check for \$500 made out to the Board of Registered Nursing.

Mail to: California Board of Registered Nursing ATTN: Continuing Education Program

P.O. Box 944210
Sacramento, CA
94244-2100

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INFORMATION COLLECTION AND ACCESS

The Information Practices Act, Section 1798.17 Civil Code, requires the following information to be provided when collecting information from individuals.

Agency Name: BOARD OF REGISTERED NURSING
Title of official responsible for information maintenance: EXECUTIVE OFFICER
Address: Telephone Number: P.O. BOX 944210, SACRAMENTO, CA 94244-2100 (916) 322-3350
Authority which authorizes the maintenance of the information: SECTION 30, SECTION 2732.1(a), BUSINESS AND PROFESSIONS CODE
ALL INFORMATION IS MANDATORY.
The consequences, if any of not providing all or any part of the requested information: FAILURE TO PROVIDE ANY OF THE REQUESTED INFORMATION WILL RESULT IN THE APPLICATION BEING REJECTED AS INCOMPLETE.
The principal purpose(s) for which the information is to be used: TO DETERMINE ELIGIBILITY FOR LICENSURE. YOUR U.S. SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER/ITIN WILL BE USED FOR PURPOSES OF TAX ENFORCEMENT, CHILD SUPPORT ENFORCEMENT AND VERIFICATION OF LICENSURE AND EXAMINATION STATUS. SECTION 30 OF THE BUSINESS AND PROFESSIONS CODE AND PUBLIC LAW 94-455 (42 USCA 405(c)(3)(C)) AUTHORIZE COLLECTION OF YOUR U.S. SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER/ITIN. IF YOU FAIL TO DISCLOSE YOUR U.S. SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER/ITIN, YOU WILL BE REPORTED TO THE FRANCHISE TAX BOARD, WHICH MAY ASSESS A \$100 PENALTY AGAINST YOU. YOUR NAME AND ADDRESS LISTED ON THIS APPLICATION WILL BE DISCLOSED TO THE PUBLIC UPON REQUEST IF AND WHEN YOU BECOME LICENSED.

Any known or foreseeable interagency or intergovernmental transfer which may be made of the information:

POSSIBLE TRANSFER TO LAW ENFORCEMENT, OTHER GOVERNMENT AGENCIES AND REPORTING U.S. SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBER/ITIN TO THE FRANCHISE TAX BOARD OR FOR CHILD SUPPORT ENFORCEMENT PURPOSES PURSUANT TO SECTION 30 OF THE BUSINESS AND PROFESSIONS CODE.

EACH INDIVIDUAL HAS THE RIGHT TO REVIEW THE FILES ON RECORDS MAINTAINED ON THEM BY THE AGENCY, UNLESS THE RECORDS ARE EXEMPT FROM DISCLOSURE.

MANDATORY REPORTER

Under California law each person licensed by the Board of Registered Nursing is a "Mandated Reporter" for child abuse or neglect purposes. Prior to commencing his or her employment, and as a prerequisite to that employment, all mandated reporters must sign a statement on a form provided to him or her by his or her employer to the effect that he or she has knowledge of the provisions of Section 11166 and will comply with those provisions.

California Penal Code Section 11166 requires that all mandated reporters make a report to an agency specified in Penal Code Section 11165.9 [generally law enforcement agencies] whenever the mandated reporter, in his or her professional capacity or within the scope of his or her employment, has knowledge of or observes a child whom the mandated reporter knows or reasonably suspects has been the victim of child abuse or neglect. The mandated reporter must make a report to the agency immediately or as soon as is practicably possible by telephone, and the mandated reporter must prepare and send a written report thereof within 36 hours of receiving the information concerning the incident.

Failure to comply with the requirements of Section 11166 is a misdemeanor, punishable by up to six months in a county jail, by a fine of one thousand dollars (\$1,000), or by both imprisonment and fine

APPENDIX I

ELECTRONIC LEARNING MODULE: CERTIFICATION OF COMPLETION

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This is to certify that

NAME

RN License #: xxxxxx

participating in:

*Emergency Department Standardized Procedure:
A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage*

xx/xx/2019
Date

Thoa Trinh Wallace DNP, MSN, RN
Facilitator

Provider approved by the California Board of Registered Nursing, Provider # xxxx, for 1.8 Contact Hours
The RN should retain this document for a period of 4 years after the course completion period.

APPENDIX J

ELECTRONIC LEARNING MODULE: FLYER

Emergency Department TRIAGE

Emergency Department Standardized Procedure: A Diagnostic Protocol for Triage

Come learn the clinical approach to accurately diagnose common chief complaints in the Emergency Department.

The course will improve your skills and scientific knowledge for triaging patients using standardized protocols.

The learning module will take approximately 1.5 hours to complete.

Course instructor:
Katrina Wallace DNP, RN

Provider approved by the
California Board of Registered Nursing,
Provider Number XXX,
for 1.8 contact hours

TRIAGE NURSE

Course Goal:

The course goal is to provide the triage nurse and other health professionals a clinical approach to accurately and efficiently diagnose common chief complaints in an Emergency Department triage. Information presented is organized in a problem-solving process that includes: Chief complaint, Definition, Symptoms, Pathophysiology, Physical Findings, Diagnostic Studies, and Potential Differential Diagnosis.

Course Contents Include:
Patient Interview
Physical examination
Standard Procedure Policy
Problem-solving Process
Common Chief Complaints

APPENDIX L

PRE- AND POST-INTERVENTION SURVEYS

Standard Procedure Pre-Intervention Survey

Age: _____ Male _____ Female _____
 Years RN experience: _____ Years triage experience: _____

Answer the following questions:	1 = Least Agree 5 = Most Agree				
1. Having a standardized procedure in triage would make triaging patients easier.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Having a standardized procedure will allow me to initiate protocol orders that I otherwise would not be able to do so without a ED MD order.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Standardized order will help initiate patient treatments sooner and move patients through faster.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Having a standardized protocol does not make a difference in the time the patients enters and leaves the ED.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Standardized orders will allow for a consistent way of triaging.	1	2	3	4	5
6. I think it is important to have standardized procedure in triage.	1	2	3	4	5
7. I can order what I think is necessary for each patient aside from the standardized protocols.	1	2	3	4	5
8. I'm concern that having standardized protocols will slow me down.	1	2	3	4	5
9. I'm concern that standardized protocols will be difficult to do.	1	2	3	4	5
10. I wish we started using standardized protocol officially sooner in triage than just now.	1	2	3	4	5

Standard Procedure Post- Intervention Survey

Age: _____ Male _____ Female _____

Years RN experience: _____ Years triage experience: _____

Answer the following questions:	1 = Least Agree	5 = Most Agree			
1. Having a standardized procedure in triage would make triaging patients easier.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Having a standardized procedure will allow me to initiate protocol orders that I otherwise would not be able to do so without a ED MD order.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Standardized order will help initiate patient treatments sooner and move patients to the treatment area.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Having a standardized protocol does not make a difference in the time the patients enter and leave the ED.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Standardized orders will allow for a consistent way of triaging.	1	2	3	4	5
6. I think it is important to have standardized procedure in triage.	1	2	3	4	5
7. I can order what I think is necessary for each patient aside from the SP	1	2	3	4	5
8. I'm concern that having standardized protocols will slow me down.	1	2	3	4	5
9. I'm concern that standardized protocols will be difficult to do.	1	2	3	4	5
10. I wish we started using standardized protocol officially sooner in triage than just now.	1	2	3	4	5
11. I feel confident the orders initiated with the standard protocol will be the same orders that the ED physician would also order.	1	2	3	4	5

13. Name what you liked and didn't like about using the standardized protocol.

14. Name 3 things that you think could improve the triage process or help improve patient flow?

15. What are some recommendations do you have to make the standard protocol better?

Thank you for your participation!

APPENDIX M
INFORMATION LETTER TO PARTICIPANTS

**Improving Emergency Department Throughput: Initiation of a
New Standardized Protocol**

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Jean O'Neil, DNP, FNP-BC, Assistant Professor of Nursing at California State University, Los Angeles and Katrina Wallace, MSN, a doctoral student at California State University, Los Angeles DNP Consortium Program. In this study we hope to learn more about the emergency room triage process. You were selected to participate in this study since all the triage nurses are required to be educated on the new triage standardized protocol. We hope that our research will lead to improved triage times, which will improve patient safety and satisfaction.

The purpose of this study is to educate the triage nurses on how to initiate orders for patients who are waiting in the lobby for an ED bed in the treatment area. This will be done prior to the ED physician's assessment of the patient. The standard protocol has two functions:

1. To expedite the flow of the patients through the ED by allowing the triage nurses to order diagnostic tests from the standardized protocol, based on evidence-based practices, prior to seeing the MD.
2. To make the triage process a more uniformed and standardized process between all the triage nurses, thereby improving their assessment skills and comfort in ordering diagnostic tests from the standardized protocol.

Since this is a mandated class, each triage nurse will be given the time before or after their work day to take the online electronic learning class explaining the new standardized protocol. There will be an anonymous pre- and post-survey regarding your thoughts and feelings about using the standardized protocol. The class is mandatory however, these surveys are not, and you may refuse to take them. The total time anticipated for the class and surveys is approximately 1.5

hours. A certificate of completion as well as 1.8 continued education hours are provided upon the completion of the e-learning module.

We will also be collecting data regarding patient triage and discharge times pre- and post-standardized protocol class. No patient names will be included, no patients will be surveyed. No provider or nurses' names associated with the patients will be included or reported. All data is de-identified. We will only be looking at door-decision, door to admit, door to discharge times, as well as those times associated with patients who left without being seen.

There will be minimal risk to taking the class. Each participant is free to refuse to do the surveys. If they choose to do the surveys, it will be anonymous. No names are required on the survey. The survey and the online class will be sent via email as well as posted in the ED portal. Since the survey is anonymous, please print the survey and place in my mailbox when completed.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain anonymous and confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you give us permission by signing this consent form, we will protect your confidentiality. The data retrieved from the nurses' survey and patient charts reviews will be kept in locked files for up to 3 years with the principal investigator. No names or identifiers will be attached to these files.

We hope to continue our work in improving the triage process. Information from the survey and review of the patient triage and discharge times, may lead us to continue to enhance the triage process by adding more educational support classes in the future.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please email Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC at joneil3@calstatela.edu or Katrina Wallace, MSN, at katrina.wallace@csu.fullerton.edu

Thank you for your time and interest in our project.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN REVIEWED BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH. ADDITIONAL CONCERNS AND COMPLAINTS, OR QUESTIONS REGARDING YOUR RIGHTS AS A RESEARCH PARTICIPANT, SHOULD BE DIRECTED TO

THE ASSOCIATE VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH (Phone number: 323-343-5368).

I have read the above information regarding the pre- post nursing survey for the project **Improving Emergency Department Throughput: Initiation of a New Standardized Protocol**. By signing this form, I am a voluntary participant and agree to take part in this project.

Signature _____

Date _____

Name _____

Please Print